

Annex to:

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Annex A – Protocol for risk assessment for peri- and post-menopausal women taking food supplements containing isolated isoflavones

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background

EFSA has accepted a mandate upon request from the German Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung (BfR) to perform a risk assessment for peri- and post-menopausal women taking food supplements containing isolated isoflavones.

The background to this mandate, as provided by the BfR is the following:

'Isoflavones are a class of naturally occurring substances, present in a number of plants, especially in soybeans, red clover and kudzu root.

The term isoflavones refers to a group of compounds, sharing a common diphenolic structure. Daidzein and genistein are most commonly found in soybeans together with glycitein. Red clover mostly contains formononetin and biochanin A, whereas puerarin and daidzein are the main isoflavones found in kudzu root. Typically, isoflavones occur naturally in the glucoside form, rather than the respective free form (aglycones).

Isoflavones are, in their chemical structure, related to the human hormone 17β -oestradiol, and for this reason are also known under the generic term of 'phytoestrogens'. Isoflavones have shown capacity to bind to oestrogen receptors and to elicit oestrogen-like effects. For this reason their use in food supplements for the alleviation of menopausal symptoms in peri- and post-menopausal women has become increasingly popular and has been promoted as an alternative to hormone replacement therapy.

In 2007 the BfR issued an expert opinion¹ on the health assessment of isoflavones-containing food supplements in which it was concluded that, on the basis of the available evidence, it was not possible to establish a dose which could be considered safe for the use by post-menopausal women who are taking food supplements containing isolated isoflavones over a long period of time. The main safety concerns expressed in this opinion were the potential for isolated isoflavones to interfere with hormone regulated processes such as the promotion of tumour growth in the breast, hyperplasia of the endometrium and possible effects on thyroid gland functioning.

This matter was referred to EFSA in 2008, which consequently started an activity aimed at the identification and characterisation of potential hazards and benefits associated with the dietary intake of isoflavones from food, food supplements and soy infant formulae. The EFSA Panel on Dietetic Products, Nutrition and Allergies (NDA) has considered the beneficial effects of isoflavones in several scientific opinions on the substantiation of a number of health claims. However, the question of the possible health risks associated with the use of food supplements containing isolated isoflavones by peri- and postmenopausal women still needs to be assessed.'

In the Terms of Reference, as provided by the Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung (BfR), EFSA is asked, in accordance with Art. 29 (1) of Regulation (EC) No 178/2002, to provide a scientific opinion on the possible health risks associated with the intake of isolated isoflavones in food supplements by peri- and postmenopausal women.

The Terms of Reference further specify the following:

'Isolated isoflavones used in dietary supplements are defined as extracts from soybeans containing a mixture of predominantly genistein, daidzein and glycitein and isolated forms of these soy-based compounds and extracts from red clover containing a mixture of predominantly formononetin and biochanin A.

In particular the scientific opinion should:

- address the relevant available scientific evidence on the potential adverse effects associated with intake of isolated isoflavones (as defined above) in food supplements by peri- and post-menopausal women. This should include data from both human and animal studies and focus on possible harmful effects for example on mammary gland, uterus and thyroid;

¹ Updated BfR Expert Opinion No 039/2007, 3 April 2007. Available online: http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/349/isolated_isoflavones_are_not_without_risk.pdf

- if adverse effects are identified, provide indication of the underlying potential modes of action;
- provide an estimate of exposure of the target populations to the isolated isoflavones from food supplements and, if possible, advice on a safe intake level of isolated isoflavones from dietary supplements.'

This mandate was allocated to the EFSA Panel on Food Additives and Nutrient Sources added to Food (ANS) and to this end a Working Group was set up to draft the scientific opinion, as requested by the BfR.

The Working Group engaged in discussion with the requestor to further clarify the interpretation of the Terms of Reference.

Additionally, in the context of the ongoing EFSA Prometheus (PROMoting METHods for Evidence Use in Science) project (EFSA, 2015) aimed at further enhancing the methodological rigour, transparency and openness of EFSA scientific assessments, this risk assessment was chosen as a case-study to test the importance of performing the assessment in two steps, i.e. planning and implementing phase. For the planning phase of the risk assessment, the current protocol was developed with the aim of performing *a priori* the whole process of problem formulation and defining beforehand the strategy for gathering the data, the criteria for selecting and appraising the evidence and for the synthesis of the results.

The experience gained with this specific risk assessment will be used as guidance for further refinement of the Methodological Framework developed in the Prometheus project.

2. Problem formulation

2.1. Objectives of the risk assessment

This risk assessment aims to assess the risk of adverse effects associated with intake of isolated isoflavones (see section 2.4) in food supplements by peri- and post-menopausal women (see section 2.3), focusing on the effects on the mammary gland, uterus and thyroid (see section 1.4).

2.2. Target population

The target population of this risk assessment comprises peri- and post-menopausal women taking food supplements containing isolated isoflavones, as defined below (see section 1.3). The risk assessment will focus on women living in 'European/American' regions only, and will not consider other populations living in different geographical regions.

According to the definitions of menopause developed by the World Health Organization (WHO) in 1996 (WHO, 1996), the term 'natural menopause' is defined as the permanent cessation of menstruation resulting from the loss of ovarian follicular activity.

Natural menopause is recognised to have occurred after 12 consecutive months of amenorrhoea, for which there is no other obvious pathological or physiological cause. Menopause occurs with the final menstrual period (FMP), which is known with certainty only in retrospect a year or more after the event. An adequate independent biological marker does not exist.

The term 'menopausal transition' should be reserved for the period of time before the FMP when variability in the menstrual cycles is usually increased.

The term 'peri-menopause' should include the period immediately prior to the menopause (when the endocrinological, biological and clinical features of approaching menopause commence) and the first year after menopause.

The term 'post-menopause' is defined as from the FMP onwards, regardless of whether the menopause was induced or spontaneous.

The definitions above are summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Relationship between different time periods surrounding the menopause (adapted from WHO, 1996)

Moreover, the WHO definitions introduce an arbitrary cut-off point of 40 years of age to define the point below which menopause is considered to be premature. This value is to be used in the absence of reliable estimates of the distribution of age at natural menopause.

Although widely used, it is acknowledged that the WHO definitions are not fit for defining women's reproductive status for scientific investigations of the menopause transition. To overcome these limitations, in 2001 the Staging Reproductive Aging Workshop (STRAW) was convened with the aim of developing a standardised staging system for reproductive ageing in women that could be reliably used both in research and experimental settings and in clinical practice. The STRAW consensus staging system consists of seven stages, independent of age, dividing the adult female life into three broad phases: reproductive, menopausal transition and post-menopause. The whole classification system is centred on the FMP (stage 0). The STRAW consensus staging system was updated 10 years after its initial development to take into account advanced knowledge and research. The latest staging system is shown in Figure 2.

FMP

Stage	-2	-1	+1a	+1b	+1c	+2
Terminology	Menopausal transition		Post-menopause			
	Early	Late	Early			Late
	Peri-menopause					
Duration	variable	1-3 years	2 years (1 +1)	3-6 years	Remaining lifespan	
Principal criteria:						
Menstrual cycle	Variable length persistent \geq 7-day difference in length of consecutive cycles	Interval of amenorrhea \geq 60 days				
Supportive criteria:						
Endocrine						
FSH	\uparrow Variable	$\uparrow > 25$ IU/L	\uparrow Variable	Stabilizes		
AMH	Low	Low	Low	Low		
Inhibin B	Low	Low	Low	Low		
Antral Follicle count 2-10 mm	Low	Low	Very low	Very low		
Descriptive characteristics						
Symptoms		Vasomotor symptoms: likely	Vasomotor symptoms: most likely			Increasing symptoms of urogenital atrophy

Figure 2: STRAW+10 staging system for reproductive ageing in women (adapted from Harlow et al., 2012)

Since there is not a single, agreed, conventional definition for peri- and post-menopausal women that can be used for this risk assessment, the following approach has been applied to identify a possible age range that could serve as a proxy for the menopausal status.

Soy isoflavones have been subject to scientific assessment by the NDA Panel with respect to their potential beneficial effects on the maintenance of bone mineral density and reduction of vasomotor symptoms in the target population of peri- and post-menopausal women (EFSA NDA Panel, 2011, 2012). It is assumed that the target population of this risk assessment will have similar characteristics to the women enrolled in the intervention trials that were provided in support of the health claims. From the two scientific opinions published, data have been extracted with respect to the age at baseline of the women enrolled and their classification in terms of menopausal status. Based on the age of the women enrolled in the studies considered for these opinions (EFSA NDA Panel, 2011, 2012), in cases when it was not possible to discriminate between peri- and post-menopausal populations, an age range of 40–75 years will be used as a proxy for combined peri- and post-menopausal status for the purpose of this risk assessment.

The scope of the current risk assessment does not cover induced menopause, e.g. by means of surgery or medical treatment.

The following sub-populations of peri- and post-menopausal women are considered of special interest and, as such, if data allow, they will be analysed separately:

- women with past medical history of cancer in any of the three target organs;
- women on treatment with anti-oestrogens;
- women with hypothyroidism taking thyroxin.

2.3. Isoflavones of concern and route of exposure

This risk assessment is limited to the oral exposure to isoflavones from food supplements (sometimes referred to as dietary supplements), in addition to their normal intake via the diet.

Food supplements are defined in Directive 2002/46/EC² as follows: 'foodstuffs the purpose of which is to supplement the normal diet and which are concentrated sources of nutrients or other substances with a nutritional or physiological effect, alone or in combination, marketed in dose form, namely forms such as capsules, pastilles, tablets, pills and other similar forms, sachets of powder, ampoules of liquids, drop dispensing bottles, and other similar forms of liquids and powders designed to be taken in measured small unit quantities.' This same definition has been used for this risk assessment.

The exposure/intervention considered for this risk assessment is supplementation with isoflavones by means of oral dosage formulations.

The term 'isoflavones' covers a wide range of substances, naturally occurring in a wide range of plants (e.g. soy, lucerne, peanuts, beans), and as such they are consumed as part of the diet.

For the purpose of this risk assessment, the term 'isolated isoflavones' consists of the substances identified in Table 1 when used in food supplements individually (e.g. genistein alone), as mixtures (e.g. as found in extracts from soy, red clover or kudzu root) or in combination with other compounds (e.g. formulations containing isoflavones in combination with *Lactobacillus*).

The isoflavones listed in Table 1 are those that have been agreed with the requestor of the mandate.

These substances shown in Table 1 will inform the search strings used to conduct the literature searches that will be used for gathering the available evidence (see section 3.2).

Table 1: Isoflavones of concern for the risk assessment

Isoflavone	Chemical structure ^(a)	CAS Registry Number ^(a)	Chemical formula ^(a)	Chemical name (<i>synonyms</i>) ^(a)
Aglycones				
Daidzein		486-66-8	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₄	7-Hydroxy-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4-benzopyrone
Genistein		446-72-0	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₅	5,7-Dihydroxy-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4-benzopyrone
Glycitein		40957-83-3	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₅	7,4'-Dihydroxy-6-methoxyisoflavone (<i>glycitin aglycone</i>)
Formononetin		485-72-3	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₄	7-Hydroxy-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-benzopyrone (<i>biochanin B</i>)
Biochanin A		491-80-5	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₅	5,7-Dihydroxy-3-p-methoxyphenyl-4H-chromen-4-one

² Directive 2002/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 June 2002 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to food supplements. OJ L 183, 12.7.2002, p. 51–57.

Isoflavone	Chemical structure ^(a)	CAS Registry Number ^(a)	Chemical formula ^(a)	Chemical name (<i>synonyms</i>) ^(a)
Prunetin		552-59-0	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₅	5-Hydroxy-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-7-methoxy-4-benzopyrone
Pratensein		2284-31-3	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₆	4H-1-Benzopyran-4-one, 5,7-dihydroxy-3-(3-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl) (<i>hydroxybiochanin A</i>)
Pseudobaptigenin		90-29-9	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₅	4H-1-Benzopyran-4-one, 3-(1,3-benzodioxol-5-yl)-7-hydroxy-
Irilone		41653-81-0	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₆	8H-1,3-Dioxolo[4,5-g][1]benzopyran-8-one, 9-hydroxy-7-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-
Calycosin		20575-57-9	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₅	4H-1-Benzopyran-4-one, 7-hydroxy-3-(3-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-
Orobol		480-23-9	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆	4H-1-Benzopyran-4-one, 3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-5,7-dihydroxy-
Glucosides				
Daidzin		552-66-9	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₉	4H-1-Benzopyran-4-one, 7-(β-D-glucopyranosyloxy)-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)- (<i>daidzein 7-O-glucoside</i>)
Genistin		529-59-9	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₀	4H-1-Benzopyran-4-one, 7-(β-D-glucopyranosyloxy)-5-hydroxy-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)- (<i>genistein 7-O-glucoside</i>)
Glycitin		40246-10-4	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ O ₁₀	4H-1-Benzopyran-4-one, 7-(β-D-glucopyranosyloxy)-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-6-methoxy- (<i>glycitein 7-O-glucoside</i>)

Isoflavone	Chemical structure ^(a)	CAS Registry Number ^(a)	Chemical formula ^(a)	Chemical name (<i>synonyms</i>) ^(a)
Puerarin		3681-99-0	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₉	4H-1-Benzopyran-4-one, 8-β-D-glucopyranosyloxy-7-hydroxy-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)- (<i>daidzein 8-C-glucoside</i>)
Isoflavones metabolites				
S-Equol		531-95-3	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₃	(S)-3,4-Dihydro-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-2H-1-benzopyran-7-ol
Dihydrodaidzein		17238-05-0	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₄	2H-1-Benzopyran-7-ol, 3,4-dihydro-3-(4-hydroxyphenyl)-, (3S)-
O-Desmethyldangolensin		21255-69-6	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄	2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl p-hydroxyphenethyl ketone (<i>O-DMA</i>)

(a): From SciFinder, online.

2.4. Adverse effects and endpoints

The current risk assessment is specifically focused on the adverse effects associated with the intake of isoflavones contained in food supplements on three target organs: the mammary gland, uterus and thyroid.

Both final and surrogate endpoints will be considered for hazard assessment. For the purpose of the current risk assessment, final endpoints are considered to be the most direct, or applicable, to the assessment, e.g. incidence of breast cancer. Surrogate endpoints are relevant but less direct, and can include upstream indicators, risk factors, intermediate outcomes or measures related to the final endpoints, i.e. pre-neoplastic lesions. Adverse effects (final and surrogate endpoints) for human and animal studies identified by the EFSA Working Group after internal discussion and taking into account the outcome of an outsourced project for the scoping of the recent available literature³ are illustrated in Table 2.

³ <http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/supporting/pub/877e>

Table 2: Adverse effects (final and surrogate endpoints) for the three target organs of concern

Type of study and target organ	Final endpoint	Surrogate endpoints
Human studies		
Mammary gland	Cancer incidence/mortality	Histopathological changes Increase in mammographic density Proliferation markers (e.g. Ki-67 labelling index) Other adverse events
Uterus	Cancer incidence/mortality	Increase in endometrial thickness Histopathological changes Pathological cervical smear test Vaginal bleeding Other adverse events
Thyroid	Cancer incidence/mortality Hypo- or hyper-thyroidism Goitre	Changes in circulating thyroid hormone levels (fT ₃ , fT ₄), thyrotropin and appearance of thyroid antibodies Increased levels of calcitonin Other adverse events
Animal studies		
Mammary gland	Increased incidence of benign or malignant tumours	Mammary gland epithelial proliferation Histopathological changes: atypical hyperplasia, epithelial metaplasia, increased inflammation, carcinoma <i>in situ</i> Proliferation markers (e.g. Ki-67 labelling index)
Uterus	Increased incidence of benign or malignant tumours	Increased uterine weight Histopathological changes: endometrial area, number of endometrial glands, squamous metaplasia, increased number of eosinophils, endometrial vessels/area, epithelial cell proliferation, uterine epithelial height Endometrial or myometrial thickness Vaginal epithelial thickness
Thyroid	Increased incidence of benign or malignant tumours Hypo- or hyperthyroidism	Changes in circulating thyroid hormones levels (fT ₃ , fT ₄ , thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH)) Weight of thyroid Histopathological changes other than tumours: epithelial proliferation, C-cells hyperplasia

Furthermore, data on absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME), genotoxicity and the molecular effects on cells, tissues and organs will be collected and evaluated as additional supporting evidence. The type of information to be gathered for the assessment is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Other supporting evidence to be considered in the risk assessment

Supporting information	Type of study
ADME	Animal and human studies
Genotoxicity	<i>In vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> studies
Oestrogen-mediated activity (mammary gland, uterus)	Oestrogen receptor binding affinity Oestrogen receptor transactivation Steroidogenesis MCF-7 cell proliferation assay Other assays
Thyroid gland mechanism	Thyroid hormone receptor transactivation Thyroid peroxidase activity Other assays
Other mechanisms (e.g. immunomodulation, redox activity, modulation of transporters)	<i>In vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> studies

2.5. Identification of the focused risk assessment sub-questions

This section illustrates the objectives of each risk assessment pillar (i.e. hazard identification, hazard characterisation and exposure assessment) and identifies the risk assessment sub-questions that were answered and combined for performing the assessment (see Table 4).

A risk assessment sub-question is defined as a question that aims to estimate a parameter and does not need to be further broken down to be answered (e.g. questions on the association between exposure and outcome or questions on occurrence or consumption).

It should be kept in mind that, in this specific case, albeit terminology has been borrowed from the general principles for risk assessment of chemicals in food, this protocol is in fact suited to a focused risk assessment of isolated isoflavones concerning the three target organs and the specific population of interest.

The objective of the assessment is to establish if there is an association between the specified isoflavones (as defined in Table 1) and the relevant adverse effects listed in Table 2, in peri- and post-menopausal women or in animal models that are considered relevant for the target population.

If an association is demonstrated, a qualitative and, if possible, quantitative description of the relationship of an agent with the endpoints of interest for this focused risk assessment will be performed. This should include an assessment of dose–response and an evaluation of possible uncertainties; for example, those derived from consideration of the toxicokinetic properties of the compounds and inter-species variability in the case of animal data are being used for deriving a health-based guidance value (HBGV⁴).

The final step of the focused risk assessment encompasses an estimation of the exposure to isoflavones from food supplements in the target population of peri- and post-menopausal women, in addition to the background dietary intake. The exposure assessment will be compared with the HBGV obtained, if any.

Table 4: Risk assessment (RA) sub-questions to be answered

RA step	Number	RA sub-question
HI	1	Is there an association between intake of isoflavones from food supplements and adverse effects on the three target organs (mammary gland, uterus and thyroid) in the human target population of peri- and post-menopausal women?
HI	2	Is there an association between diet supplemented with isolated isoflavones and adverse effects on the three target organs (mammary gland, uterus and thyroid) in experimental animals?
HI	3	Supporting data on association/adverse effects: are isolated isoflavones associated with changes at the molecular level such as mutation and other genotoxicity endpoints?
HI	4	Supporting data on association/adverse effects: are isolated isoflavones associated with modifications to the physiology or response of cells, tissues and organs (e.g. signalling pathways used by cells, oestrogenic affinity)?
HC	5	What is the nature of any dose–response relationship between supplementation with isoflavones and relevant endpoints in the three target organs in human and/or animal studies?
HC	6	What is the ADME in humans and in different animal species/strains?
HC	7	Is there a difference in ADME between humans and animals?
EA	8	What are the levels of use of isoflavones in food supplements targeted at the population of peri- and post-menopausal women in Europe?
EA	9	What is the background exposure to isoflavones from the diet in the target population?
EA	10	What is the estimate of exposure to isoflavones from food supplements in the target population?

EA, exposure assessment; HC, hazard characterisation; HI, hazard identification; RA: risk assessment.

⁴ HBGVs developed for substances found in food and drinking water are the quantitative expression of the range of oral exposure (either acute or chronic) that would be expected to be without appreciable health risk.

3. Methods for performing hazard identification of specific endpoints

The four sub-questions under hazard identification will be addressed by reviewing the literature. Sub-questions 1 and 2 will be answered by performing a full systematic review. Sub-questions 3 and 4 will be addressed using a more narrative approach.

3.1. Review questions and eligibility criteria for study selection

The selection of studies relevant to sub-question 1 will be performed using the eligibility criteria described below in Table 5.

Table 5: Eligibility criteria for sub-question 1

Is there an association between intake of isoflavones from food supplements and adverse effects on the three target organs (mammary gland, uterus and thyroid) in the human target population of peri- and post-menopausal women?		
Study design	In	Randomised controlled trials Non-randomised, comparative studies of interventions Prospective, longitudinal, observational studies Case-control studies (retrospective and nested)
	Out	Cross-sectional studies Case studies/case series Animal studies <i>In vitro</i> studies
Study characteristics	In	Intervention lasting at least 12 weeks Any number of subjects
	Out	
Population	In	Peri- and post-menopausal women Women aged 40–75 years if menopausal status is not reported Study location: Europe, America or Australia
	Out	Studies conducted in male subjects Studies conducted in both female and male subjects complying with inclusion criteria, when results cannot be analysed by gender Studies exclusively conducted in patients/subjects < 40 or > 75 years of age
Exposure/intervention	In	Measured supplementation with isoflavones (as defined in Table 1) via the oral route
	Out	Exposure to isoflavones exclusively via normal dietary intake Intervention limited to changes in the diet (e.g. by replacing some food items with soy foods) Studies not reporting either levels of isoflavones in product or regimen to allow intakes to be quantified
Specific outcome of interest	In	All endpoints (see Table 2) related to the three target organs (mammary gland, uterus, thyroid)
	Out	Studies reporting exclusively preventative/beneficial effects on other target organs (e.g. bone health)
Language of the full text	In	English
Time	In	1985–2015 ^(a)
Publication type	In	Primary research studies (i.e. studies generating new data) Systematic reviews and meta-analyses ^(b)
	Out	Narrative reviews Expert opinions, editorials and letters to the editors Meetings' abstracts and posters

(a): An update of the literature search was performed in 2015, covering until 23 June 2015.

(b): Systematic reviews, including meta-analyses, on this topic that will be identified during the process of literature screening studies will be collected for the purposes of reviewing the reference list but will not be considered to contribute to the final number of studies considered eligible unless they also contain original data.

The selection of studies relevant to sub-question 2 will be performed using the eligibility criteria described below in Table 6.

Table 6: Eligibility criteria for sub-question 2

Is there an association between supplementation with isolated isoflavones and adverse effects on the three target organs (mammary gland, uterus and thyroid) in experimental animals?		
Study design	In	Experimental animal studies
	Out	Human studies <i>In vitro</i> studies
Study characteristics	In	Intervention lasting at least 5 days At least five animals/dose group
	Out	
Population	In	Ovariectomised and/or non-juvenile mammals (all species, all strains)
	Out	Studies conducted in male animals Studies conducted in both female and male animals complying with inclusion criteria, when results are not reported separately for each sex Animal models of progression of cancer, e.g. medroxyprogesterone acetate (MPA)-accelerated breast cancer in 7,12-dimethylbenz(a)anthracene (DMBA)-induced or xenograft mammary cancer models (these studies will, however, be collected for possible mode of action analyses) Immunodeficient animal models, e.g. knock-out models (these studies will, however, be collected for possible mode of action analyses)
Exposure/intervention	In	Supplementation with isoflavones (as defined in Table 1) via the oral route
	Out	Supplementation <i>in utero</i> , during gestation or early post-natal or started before ovariectomy Exposure to isoflavones exclusively via normal dietary intake (e.g. normal chow, with no control) Studies not reporting the level of isoflavones administered to the animals to allow intakes to be quantified
Specific outcome of interest	In	All endpoints (see Table 2) related to the three target organs (mammary gland, uterus, thyroid)
	Out	Studies reporting exclusively preventative/beneficial effects on other target organs (e.g. bone health)
Language of the full text	In	English
Time	In	1985–2015 ^(a)
Publication type	In	Primary research studies (i.e. studies generating new data) Systematic reviews and meta-analyses ^(b)
	Out	Narrative reviews Expert opinions, editorials and letters to the editors Meetings' abstracts and posters

(a): An update of the literature search was performed in 2015, covering until 23 June 2015.

(b): Systematic reviews, including meta-analyses, on this topic that will be identified during the process of literature screening studies will be collected for the purposes of reviewing the reference list but will not be considered to contribute to the final number of studies considered eligible unless they also contained original data.

The literature search and subsequent selection of studies relevant to sub-question 3 will be performed using the criteria described in Table 7.

Table 7: Criteria informing literature search and eligibility of studies considered for sub-question 3

Are isolated isoflavones associated with changes at the molecular level such as mutation and other genotoxicity endpoints?		
Study design/test systems	In	Bacterial reverse mutation test in <i>Salmonella</i> Typhimurium (TA1535, TA1537 or TA97a or TA97, TA98, TA100, TA102 <i>S. Typhimurium</i> tester strains) and <i>Escherichia coli</i> (<i>E. coli</i> WP2 strain)
		<i>In vitro:</i> Mammalian cell gene mutation test in Chinese hamster ovary (CHO), v79 Chinese hamster fibroblasts, human or other mammalian peripheral blood lymphocytes Mammalian chromosome aberration test in CHO, v79 Chinese hamster fibroblasts, human peripheral blood lymphocytes Mammalian cell micronucleus test in CHO, v79 Chinese hamster fibroblasts, human peripheral blood lymphocytes Sister chromatid exchange (SCE) assay in mammalian cells Unscheduled DNA synthesis (UDS) test with mammalian cells Transformation assay in 3T3 mouse cells
		<i>In vivo:</i> Mammalian micronucleus test Mammalian chromosome aberration test Rodent dominant lethal test UDS test with mammalian liver cells Mammalian alkaline comet assay
	Out	Test systems: <i>Drosophila melanogaster</i> , <i>Vicia faba</i> , <i>Allium cepa</i> , fishes
Exposure/intervention	In	Route of exposure for <i>in vivo</i> : oral, subcutaneous, intraperitoneal
	Out	Intravenous, epidermal
Specific outcome of interest	In	Gene (point) mutation Structural and numerical chromosomal aberrations Micronuclei Endoreduplication, polyploidy SCEs UDS/DNA repair Cell transformation
Language of the full text	In	English
Time	In	1995–2014 ^(a)
Publication type	In	Primary research studies (i.e. studies generating new data)
	Out	Editorials Narrative reviews

(a): The starting date was chosen to cover published studies performed after the establishment of international guidelines for genotoxicity testing.

The literature search and subsequent selection of studies relevant to sub-question 4 will be performed using the criteria described in Table 8.

Table 8: Criteria informing literature search and eligibility of studies considered for sub-question 4

Are isolated isoflavones associated with modifications to the physiology or response of cells, tissues and organs (e.g. signalling pathways used by cells, (anti-)oestrogenic activity)?		
Study design/test systems	In	Proliferation of oestrogen-dependent cancer cells (MCF-7, T47D, etc.) in <i>in vitro</i> and xenograft <i>in vivo</i> models <i>In vitro</i> OECD test guidelines providing mechanistic information (e.g. TG 455, TG 456, TG 457) <i>In vivo</i> uterotrophic assay (OECD TG 440) Aromatase activity Thyroid peroxidase inhibition assay Thyroid hormone-binding protein assays Transactivation reporter assay
Exposure/intervention	In	Route of exposure for <i>in vivo</i> : oral, subcutaneous, intraperitoneal, intravenous Cut-off concentrations for <i>in vitro</i> studies investigating receptor activity and steroid synthesis: cytotoxic concentrations, as tested by a cytotoxicity test (e.g. MTS) No cut-off concentration for proliferation assays, such as the MCF-7 test
	Out	Route of exposure: epidermal
Specific outcome of interest	In	Proliferation of oestrogen-dependent cancer cells Oestrogen receptor binding affinity Oestrogen receptor transactivation Steroidogenesis Uterotrophic assay <i>in vivo</i> Activation of oestrogen-regulated genes Thyroid peroxidase enzyme activity Thyroid hormone receptor transactivation
Language of the full text	In	English
Time	In	2010–2014 ^(a)
Publication type	In	Reviews Primary research studies (i.e. studies generating new data)
	Out	Expert opinions, editorials and letters to the editor

(a): Starting date was chosen by the Working Group to limit search to most recent reviews.

3.2. Literature searches

For sub-questions 1 and 2 an extensive literature search will be performed in bibliographic databases and sources of grey literature.

The following bibliographic databases will be searched:

- Web of Science, encompassing the following databases:
 - Web of Science™ Core Collection (1975–present);
 - BIOSIS Citation IndexSM (1926–present);
 - CABI: CAB Abstracts[®] (1910–present);
 - Chinese Science Citation Database (1989–present);
 - Current Contents Connect[®] (1998–present);
 - Data Citation IndexSM (1900–present);
 - FSTA[®]—the food science resource (1969–present);
 - MEDLINE[®] (1950–present);
 - SciELO Citation Index (1997–present)—access to scholarly literature in sciences, social sciences, arts and humanities published in leading open access journals from Latin America, Portugal, Spain and South Africa;

- Zoological Record (1864–present)—the world’s leading taxonomic reference and oldest continuing database of animal biology;
- Embase;
- Cochrane Library;
- Scopus;
- Toxline.

Ongoing trials databases will also be searched, namely:

- The US National Institutes of Health Ongoing Trials Register on www.clinicaltrials.gov
- The WHO International Clinical Trials Registry Platform on www.who.int/trialsearch

The following sources of grey literature will be searched:

- WHO International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) on <http://www.iarc.fr/index.php>
- WHO International Programme on Chemical Safety (IPCS) on <http://www.who.int/ipcs>

The search strategies and specific terminology for the bibliographic databases and the queries used for the sources of grey literature are reported in Tables 9–14.

- For sub-questions 3 and 4, a narrower search will be conducted on Web of Science, encompassing all the databases described above and covering the vast majority of the published relevant studies. Specific search strings, encompassing terminology related to standard testing for genotoxicity and endocrine disruptor activity, will be used to search published literature (see Tables 15–16).
- For all sub-questions, the output from the searched databases, including all indexed fields per hit (e.g. title, authors, abstract), will be exported into separate Endnote X5 files, allowing a count of the individual hits per database. Files will then be combined and duplicate records will be removed.

The files obtained will be transferred into DistillerSR[®] Web-Based Systematic Review Software (Evidence Partners, Ottawa, Canada) for the selection procedure (see section 2.3). Using the Distiller duplicate function, duplicates will be identified and removed (quarantined).

Table 9: Details of search strings used for literature searches in support of review sub-questions 1 and 2—search strings for Web of Science

Set number	Search	Commentary
20	#14 NOT #19	Isoflavones AND cancers of interest excluding narrative reviews
19	#15 NOT (#16 OR #17 OR #18)	Reviews that are likely not to be systematic reviews
18	TS=meta-analysis	Records with mention of meta-analysis
17	TS=(systematic near/2 review)	Records with mention of systematic review
16	DT=meta-analysis	Records indexed as meta-analyses
15	DT=review	All types of review
14	(#12 not #13) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=1985-2014	Records remaining after record types removed
13	(#12) AND LANGUAGE: (English) AND DOCUMENT TYPES: (Addresses OR Bibliography OR Biography OR Case Reports OR Editorial OR In Vitro OR Interview OR Lectures OR Letter OR News OR Newspaper Article OR Patient Education Handout OR Portraits) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=1985-2014	Record types that are not of interest
12	(#4 and (#7 or #8 or #11)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=1985-2014	Isoflavones combined with each of the set combinations (i.e. highly specific, surrogate endpoints and less specific surrogate endpoints)

Set number	Search	Commentary
11	#10 AND #9 Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=1985-2014	Non-specific adverse effects combined with organs of interest
10	(TS=(BREAST OR MAMMARY OR MAMMOGRAPHIC OR ENDOMETRIAL OR ENDOMETRIUM OR UTERINE OR UTERUS OR THYROID OR GOITRE? OR GOITER?)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=1985-2014	Organs of interest
9	(Ts=('Adverse effect' OR 'ADVERSE EFFECTS' OR HISTOPATHOLOG* OR 'TISSUE DENSITY' OR Calcitonin OR Inflammation OR Apoptosis OR 'Anti-oxidative defense' OR 'Anti-oxidant?' OR 'Cox 2' OR 'Cyclo oxygenase' OR 'Arachidonic acid?' OR Alipoxygenase OR 'Platelet aggregation' OR (Cell* NEAR/4 adhesion) OR angiogenesis OR 'cell cycle' OR 'nk cells' or (EPITHELIAL NEAR/3 (PROLIFERAT* OR METAPLASIA OR HEIGHT OR THICKNESS)) OR HYPERPLASIA OR 'K1 67' OR K167 OR 'TUMOR MARKER?' OR 'TUMOUR MARKER?' OR 'BIOLOGICAL MARKER?' OR 'PROLIFERATION MARKER?' OR 'PAP SMEAR?' OR 'PAP TEST*' OR 'VAGINAL SMEAR?' OR 'CERVICAL SCREEN*' OR 'CERVICAL TEST?' OR 'Papanicolaou TEST*' OR 'Papanicolaou SMEAR?') OR mh:Exp=(apoptosis or Antioxidant response elements OR Cyclooxygenase 2 or arachidonic acids OR Lipoxygenases OR angiogenesis modulating agents OR cell cycle OR killer cells, natural or TUMOR? OR TUMOURS? OR 'SQUAMOUS METAPLASIA' OR EOSINOPHILS OR 'TUMOR MARKERS, BIOLOGICAL' OR 'BIOLOGICAL MARKERS' OR 'VAGINAL SMEARS')) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=1985-2014	Non-specific adverse effects
8	(TS=(MAMMOGRAPHIC DENSITY OR (Endometr* NEAR/3 thickness) OR ENDOMETRIAL AREA OR ENDOMETRIAL GLAND? OR ENDOMETRIAL VESSEL? OR (VAGINAL NEAR/3 BLEED*) OR (UTERINE NEAR/3 BLEED*) OR (UTERUS NEAR/3 BLEED*) OR (UTERINE NEAR/3 WEIGHT) OR (UTERUS NEAR/3 WEIGHT) OR (MYOMETRIAL NEAR/3 THICKNESS) OR (VAGINAL NEAR/4 THICKNESS) OR Hypothyroidism OR Hyperthyroidism OR thyroid hormone level? OR Ft3 OR Ft4 OR Thyrotropin OR Thyroid antibodies OR THYROID WEIGHT) or Mh:Exp=(uterine haemorrhage OR hyperthyroidism OR Immunoglobulins, thyroid-stimulating)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=1985-2014	Surrogate markers specific to organs of interest
7	#6 OR #5 Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=1985-2014	Cancers of interest combined
6	(TS=(BREAST NEAR/4 (CANCER* OR NEOPLASM? OR SARCOMA? OR CARCINOMA?)) OR TS=(MAMMAR* NEAR/4 (CANCER* OR NEOPLASM? OR SARCOMA? OR CARCINOMA?)) OR TS=(UTERUS NEAR/4 (CANCER* OR NEOPLASM? OR SARCOMA? OR CARCINOMA?)) OR TS=(UTERINE NEAR/4 (CANCER* OR NEOPLASM? OR SARCOMA? OR CARCINOMA?)) OR TS=(ENDOMETRI* NEAR/4 (CANCER* OR NEOPLASM? OR SARCOMA? OR CARCINOMA?)) OR TS=(THYROID NEAR/4 (CANCER* OR NEOPLASM? OR SARCOMA? OR CARCINOMA?)) OR TS=(GOITRE? OR GOITER?) or TS=(leiomyoma? OR fibroid?)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=1985-2014	Text words indicating cancers of interest
5	(MH:EXP=(BREAST NEOPLASMS OR UTERINE NEOPLASMS OR THYROID NEOPLASMS OR GOITER OR LEIOMYOMA)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=1985-2014	Cancer of organs of interest
4	#3 OR #2 OR #1 Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=1985-2014	Combines the isoflavone sets
3	(MH:EXP=(SOYBEANS OR MEDICAGO SATIVA OR TRIFOLIUM)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=1985-2014	Finds the mesh terms for isoflavones not captured by set 1
2	(Rn=(486-66-8 Or 446-72-0 OR 485-72-3 OR 491-80-5 OR 41653-81-0 OR 40957-83-3 OR 552-59-0 OR 2284-31-3 OR 90-29-9 OR 20575-57-9 OR 480-23-9 OR 552-66-9 OR 529-59-9 OR 40246-10-4 OR 3681-99-0 OR 531-95-3 OR 17238-05-0 OR 21255-69-6)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=1985-2014	Finds isoflavones with registry numbers
1	(TS=(ISOFLAVONES OR 'RED CLOVER' OR KUDZU OR SOY OR SOYBEAN OR SOYBEANS OR PUERARIA OR DAIDZEIN OR GENISTEIN OR FORMONONETIN OR 'BIOCHANIN A' OR IRILONE OR GLYCITEIN OR PRUNETIN OR PRATENSEIN OR PSEUDOBAPTIGENIN OR CALYCOSIN OR OROBOL OR DAIDZIN OR GENISTIN OR GLYCITIN OR PUERARIN OR 'S EQUOL' OR DIHYDRODAIDZEIN OR 'O DESMETHYLANGOLENSIN' OR 'O DMA' OR PHYTOESTROGEN? OR PHYTOOESTROGEN?)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=1985-2014	Finds isoflavones in title, abstract and mesh

Table 10: Details of search strings used for literature searches in support of review sub-questions 1 and 2—search strings for Web of Science without MEDLINE

Set number	Search	Commentary
9	(#7) AND LANGUAGE: (English) AND DOCUMENT TYPES: (Article OR Abstract of Published Item OR Book OR Book Chapter OR Meeting Abstract OR Proceedings Paper) Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, CPCI-S Timespan=1985-2014	Results EXCLUDING reviews
8	(#7) AND LANGUAGE: (English) AND DOCUMENT TYPES: (Article OR Book OR Book Chapter OR Meeting Abstract OR Proceedings Paper OR Review) Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, CPCI-S Timespan=1985-2014	Results INCLUDING reviews
7	(#1 AND (#2 OR #3 or #6)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, CPCI-S Timespan=1985-2014	ISOFLAVONES AND (ORGANS OF INTEREST, CHANGES IN ORGANS OR INTEREST, ORGANS OF INTEREST AND CHANGES)
6	(#4 AND #5) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, CPCI-S Timespan=1985-2014	Combines CHANGES and ORGANS of interest
5	(TS=(BREAST OR MAMMARY OR MAMMOGRAPHIC OR ENDOMETRIAL OR ENDOMETRIUM OR UTERINE OR UTERUS OR THYROID OR GOITER?) OR GOITER?) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, CPCI-S Timespan=1985-2014	ORGANS
4	Ts=('Adverse effect' OR 'ADVERSE EFFECTS' OR HISTOPATHOLOG* OR 'TISSUE DENSITY' OR Calcitonin OR Inflammation OR Apoptosis OR 'Anti-oxidative defense' OR 'Anti-oxidant?' OR 'Cox 2' OR 'Cyclo oxygenase' OR 'Arachidonic acid?' OR Alipoxygenase OR 'Platelet aggregation' OR (Cell* NEAR/4 adhesion) OR angiogenesis OR 'cell cycle' OR 'nk cells' or (EPITHELIAL NEAR/3 (PROLIFERAT* OR METAPLASIA OR HEIGHT OR THICKNESS)) OR HYPERPLASIA OR 'K1 67' OR K167 OR 'TUMOR MARKER?' OR 'TUMOUR MARKER?' OR 'BIOLOGICAL MARKER?' OR 'PROLIFERATION MARKER?' OR 'PAP SMEAR?' OR 'PAP TEST*' OR 'VAGINAL SMEAR?' OR 'CERVICAL SCREEN*' OR 'CERVICAL TEST?' OR 'Papanicolaou TEST*' OR 'Papanicolaou SMEAR?') AND ENGLISH Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, CPCI-S Timespan=1985-2014	CHANGES
3	(TS=(MAMMOGRAPHIC DENSITY OR (Endometr* NEAR/3 thickness) OR ENDOMETRIAL AREA OR ENDOMETRIAL GLAND? OR ENDOMETRIAL VESSEL? OR (VAGINAL NEAR/3 BLEED*) OR (UTERINE NEAR/3 BLEED*) OR (UTERUS NEAR/3 BLEED*) OR (UTERINE NEAR/3 WEIGHT) OR (UTERUS NEAR/3 WEIGHT) OR (MYOMETRIAL NEAR/3 THICKNESS) OR (VAGINAL NEAR/4 THICKNESS) OR Hypothyroidism OR Hyperthyroidism OR thyroid hormone level? OR Ft3 OR Ft4 OR Thyrotropin OR Thyroid antibodies OR THYROID WEIGHT)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, CPCI-S Timespan=1985-2014	CHANGES IN ORGANS OF INTEREST
2	(TS=(BREAST NEAR/4 (CANCER* OR NEOPLASM? OR SARCOMA? OR CARCINOMA?)) OR TS=(MAMMAR* NEAR/4 (CANCER* OR NEOPLASM? OR SARCOMA? OR CARCINOMA?)) OR TS= (UTERUS NEAR/4 (CANCER* OR NEOPLASM? OR SARCOMA? OR CARCINOMA?)) OR TS= (UTERINE NEAR/4 (CANCER* OR NEOPLASM? OR SARCOMA? OR CARCINOMA?)) OR TS= (ENDOMETRI* NEAR/4 (CANCER* OR NEOPLASM? OR SARCOMA? OR CARCINOMA?)) OR TS= (THYROID NEAR/4 (CANCER* OR NEOPLASM? OR SARCOMA? OR CARCINOMA?)) OR TS=(GOITER? OR GOITER? OR leiomyoma? OR fibroid?)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, CPCI-S Timespan=1985-2014	CANCER OF TARGET ORGANS
1	(TS=(ISOFLAVONES OR RED CLOVER OR KUDZU OR SOY OR SOYBEAN OR SOYBEANS OR PUERARIA OR DAIDZEIN OR GENISTEIN OR FORMONONETIN OR 'BIOCHANIN A' OR IRILONE OR GLYCITEIN OR PRUNETIN OR PRATENSEIN OR PSEUDOBAPTIGENIN OR CALYCOSIN OR OROBOL OR DAIDZIN OR GENISTIN OR GLYCITIN OR PUERARIN OR S EQUOL OR DIHYDRODAIDZEIN OR O DESMETHYLANGOLENSIN OR O DMA OR PHYTOESTROGEN? OR PHYTOOESTROGEN?)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=SCI-EXPANDED, CPCI-S Timespan=1985-2014	ISOFLAVONES

Table 11: Details of search strings used for literature searches in support of review sub-questions 1 and 2—search strings for EMBASE <1980 to 2014 Week 39>

Set number	Search	Number of hits
91	84 not 88	3 066
90	85 not (86 or 87)	1 910 451
89	84 not 88	3 066
88	85 not (86 or 87)	1 910 451
87	exp `systematic review`/	79 975
86	meta analysis/	82 940
85	review/	1 966 306
84	83 not MEDLINE.cr.	4 122
83	81 not 82	4 423
82	(conference proceeding editorial or editorial or letter or patent or press or release or short survey or survey or trade or trade journal or trade journal article or trade journal conference paper).pt.	1 623 431
81	23 and (33 or 48 or 80)	4 646
80	or/49-79	322 048
79	((CERVICAL or PAP or PAPANICOLAOU) adj (TEST\$1 or TESTING or SCREEN or SCREENING or SMEAR\$1)).ti,ab.	14 376
78	Papanicolaou test/	12 054
77	(k167 or ki-67 or ((Tumour\$1 or tumor\$1 or BIOLOGICAL) adj marker\$1)).ti,ab.	46 354
76	exp TUMOR MARKER/	169 143
75	(LIPOXYGENASE\$1 and (BREAST or ENDOMETRIUM or MYOMETRIUM or VAGINA or THYROID or BREAST)).ti,ab.	200
74	(ENDOMETRIUM/ or MYOMETRIUM/ or VAGINA/ or THYROID/ or BREAST/) and LIPOXYGENASE/	41
73	((BREAST or THYROID or ENDOMETR\$) adj4 HYPERPLASIA).ti,ab.	5 313
72	BREAST HYPERPLASIA/ or THYROID HYPERPLASIA/ or ENDOMETRIUM HYPERPLASIA/	8 360
71	(epithelial adj4 (PROLIFERAT* or METAPLASIA or HEIGHT or THICKNESS)).ti,ab.	12 858
70	((killer adj cell\$1) or (nk adj cell\$1)) and (BREAST or ENDOMETRIUM or MYOMETRIUM or VAGINA or THYROID or BREAST)).ti,ab.	1 658
69	(ENDOMETRIUM/ or MYOMETRIUM/ or VAGINA/ or THYROID/ or BREAST/) and natural killer cell/	662
68	(angiogenesis and (BREAST or ENDOMETRIUM or MYOMETRIUM or VAGINA or THYROID or BREAST)).ti,ab.	7 009
67	(ENDOMETRIUM/ or MYOMETRIUM/ or VAGINA/ or THYROID/ or BREAST/) and angiogenesis/	1 350
66	((adhesion or aggregation) and (BREAST or ENDOMETRIUM or MYOMETRIUM or VAGINA or THYROID or BREAST)).ti,ab.	7 018
65	(ENDOMETRIUM/ or MYOMETRIUM/ or VAGINA/ or THYROID/ or BREAST/) and thrombocyte aggregation/	47
64	Alipoxygenase and (BREAST or ENDOMETRIUM or MYOMETRIUM or VAGINA or THYROID or BREAST)).ti,ab.	0
63	(arachidonic and (BREAST or ENDOMETRIUM or MYOMETRIUM or VAGINA or THYROID or BREAST)).ti,ab.	870
62	(ENDOMETRIUM/ or MYOMETRIUM/ or VAGINA/ or THYROID/ or BREAST/) and arachidonic acid/	246
61	((cox2 or cox or Cyclo oxygenase or Cyclooxygenase) and (BREAST or ENDOMETRIUM or MYOMETRIUM or VAGINA or THYROID or BREAST)).ti,ab.	8 923
60	(ENDOMETRIUM/ or MYOMETRIUM/ or VAGINA/ or THYROID/ or BREAST/) and exp cyclooxygenase 2 inhibitor/	173
59	((oxidative or oxidant) and (BREAST or ENDOMETRIUM or MYOMETRIUM or VAGINA or THYROID or BREAST)).ti,ab.	3 874
58	(ENDOMETRIUM/ or MYOMETRIUM/ or VAGINA/ or THYROID/ or BREAST/) and oxidative stress/	408
57	(ENDOMETRIUM/ or MYOMETRIUM/ or VAGINA/ or THYROID/ or BREAST/) and exp `cellular, subcellular and molecular biological phenomena and functions`/	37 877
56	((apoptosis or (cell adj cycle)) and (BREAST or ENDOMETRIUM or MYOMETRIUM or VAGINA or THYROID or BREAST)).ti,ab.	23 191
55	(inflammation and (BREAST or ENDOMETRIUM or MYOMETRIUM or VAGINA or THYROID or BREAST)).ti,ab.	5 373
54	(ENDOMETRIUM/ or MYOMETRIUM/ or VAGINA/ or THYROID/ or BREAST/) and inflammation.hw.	1 986
53	(calcitonin and (BREAST or ENDOMETRIUM or MYOMETRIUM or VAGINA or THYROID or BREAST)).ti,ab.	3 596

Set number	Search	Number of hits
52	(ENDOMETRIUM/ or MYOMETRIUM/ or VAGINA/ or THYROID/ or BREAST/) and calcitonin/	1 064
51	((Tissue adj density) and (BREAST or ENDOMETRIUM or MYOMETRIUM or VAGINA or THYROID or BREAST)).ti,ab.	183
50	((ADVERSE adj (EVENT\$1 or EFFECT\$)) and (BREAST or ENDOMETRIUM or MYOMETRIUM or VAGINA or THYROID or BREAST)).ti,ab.	9 578
49	(ENDOMETRIUM/ or MYOMETRIUM/ or VAGINA/ or THYROID/ or BREAST/) and HISTOPATHOLOGY/	3 617
48	or/34-47	114 232
47	((BREAST or MAMM\$) adj3 (DENSE or DENSITY)).ti,ab.	3 198
46	BREAST/ and DENSITY/ (832)	832
45	((Endometr\$ adj3 (thickness or AREA or GLAND\$1 or VESSEL\$1)) or (VAGINAL adj3 (BLEED\$ or THICKNESS)) or (UTER\$ adj3 (BLEED\$ or WEIGHT)) or (MYOMETRIAL adj3 THICKNESS) or Hypothyroidism or Hyperthyroidism or thyroid hormone level\$1 or Ft3 or Ft4 or Thyrotropin or Thyroid antibodies or (THYROID adj WEIGHT)).ti,ab.	77 119
44	thyroid stimulating immunoglobulin/	1 110
43	thyroid weight/	1 087
42	thyroxine blood level/ or thyroid hormone blood level/	8 978
41	hypothyroidism/	39 882
40	VAGINA/ and THICKNESS/	138
39	MYOMETRIUM/ and THICKNESS/	151
38	ENDOMETRIUM/ and THICKNESS/	740
37	uterus weight/	2 326
36	uterus bleeding/	7 587
35	vagina bleeding/	9 831
34	endometrial thickness/	676
33	or/24-32 (540 442
32	((THYROID adj4 (CANCER\$1 or NEOPLASM\$1 or SARCOMA\$1 or CARCINOMA\$1)) or (GOITRE\$1 or GOITER\$1 or LEIOMYOMA\$1 or FIBROID\$1)).ti,ab.	67 442
31	(endometri\$ adj4 (CANCER\$1 or NEOPLASM\$1 or SARCOMA\$1 or CARCINOMA\$1)).ti,ab.	27 988
30	(Uter\$ adj4 (CANCER\$1 or NEOPLASM\$1 or SARCOMA\$1 or CARCINOMA\$1)).ti,ab.	18 224
29	(MAMMAR\$1 adj4 (CANCER\$1 or NEOPLASM\$1 or SARCOMA\$1 or CARCINOMA\$1)).ti,ab.	13 167
28	(BREAST adj4 (CANCER\$1 or NEOPLASM\$1 or SARCOMA\$1 or CARCINOMA\$1)).ti,ab.	275 276
27	exp goiter/ or uterus myoma/	30 208
26	exp thyroid cancer/	36 660
25	exp uterus cancer/	105 272
24	exp breast cancer/	291 089
23	or/20,22	58 214
22	limit 21 to (english language and yr='1985 -Current')	139 655
21	(486-66-8 or 446-72-0 or 485-72-3 or 491-80-5 or 41653-81-0 or 40957-83-3 or 552-59-0 or 2284-31-3 or 90-29-9 or 20575-57-9 or 480-23-9 or 552-66-9 or 529-59-9 or 40246-10-4 or 3681-99-0 or 531-95-3 or 17238-05-0 or 21255-69-6).rn. (15224)	15 224
20	limit 19 to (english language and yr='1985 -Current')	58 213
19	or/1-18	67 848
18	(PRUNETIN or PRATENSEIN or PSEUDOBAPTIGENIN or CALYCOSIN or OROBOL or DAIDZIN or GENISTIN or GLYCITIN or PUERARIN or (S adj EQUOL) or DIHYDRODAIDZEIN or (O adj DESMETHYLANGOLENSIN) or (O adj DMA) or PHYTOESTROGEN\$1 or PHYTOOESTROGEN\$1).ti,ab. (6062)	6 062
17	(ISOFLAVONE\$1 or (RED adj CLOVER) or KUDZU or SOY or SOYBEAN\$1 or PUERARIA or DAIDZEIN or GENISTEIN or FORMONONETIN or (BIOCHANIN adj A) or IRILONE or GLYCITEIN).ti,ab.	50 968
16	phytoestrogen/	4 846
15	equol/	1 044
14	puerarin/	1 255
13	orobol/	66
12	isoflavonoid/	1 032
11	isoflavone/	3 390
10	prunetin/	114
9	glycitein/	660
8	biochanin A/	1 048

Set number	Search	Number of hits
7	formononetin/	941
6	genistein/ or genistin/	13 233
5	daidzein/ or daidzin/	4 499
4	soybean.hw.	30 955
3	exp Pueraria/	631
2	red clover/	478
1	isoflavone derivative/	5 008

Table 12: Details of search strings used for literature searches in support of review sub-questions 1 and 2—search strings for Cochrane database

Set number	Search	Commentary
3	KUDZU or SOY or SOYBEAN? or PUERARIA or DAIDZEIN or GENISTEIN or FORMONONETIN or 'BIOCHANIN A' or IRILONE or GLYCITEIN or PRUNETIN or PRATENSEIN or PSEUDOBAPTIGENIN or CALYCOSIN or OROBOL or DAIDZIN or GENISTIN or GLYCITIN or PUERARIN or 'S EQUOL' or DIHYDRODAIDZEIN or 'O DESMETHYLANGOLENSIN' or 'O DMA' or PHYTOESTROGEN? or PHYTOOESTROGEN?:ti,ab,kw	Word variations have been searched
2	`red clover':ti,ab,kw	Word variations have been searched
1	isoflavone?:ti,ab,kw	Word variations have been searched

Table 13: Details of search strings used for literature searches in support of review sub-questions 1 and 2—search strings for TOXLINE

Set number	Search	Commentary
1	(kudzu OR pueraria OR 'pueraria lobata' OR 'kudzu root' OR P810000000 [rn] OR soy OR soybean* OR pueraria OR 'pueraria lobata' OR 'kudzu root' OR kudzu OR P810000000 [rn] OR daidzein OR daidzeol OR 486-66-8 [rn] OR genistein OR 446-72-0 [rn] OR formononetin OR formononetol OR 'biochanin b' OR 485-72-3 [rn] OR biochanin OR 491-80-5 [rn] OR irilone OR glycitein OR 40957-83-3 [rn] OR prunetin OR 552-59-0 [rn] OR pratensein OR 2284-31-3 [rn] OR pseudobaptigenin OR 90-29-9 [rn] OR calycosin OR 20575-57-9 [rn] OR orobol OR isoluteolin OR 480-23-9 [rn] OR daidzin OR daidzoid OR 552-66-9 [rn] OR genistin OR genistoside OR genistine OR 'genistein glucoside' OR 529-59-9 [rn] OR glycitin OR 40246-10-4 [rn] OR puerarin OR 3681-99-0 [rn] OR equol OR 531-95-3 [rn] OR dihydrodaidzein OR 17238-05-0 [rn] OR desmethylangolensin OR dma OR 'cacodylic acid' OR 'dimethylarsinic acid' OR 'hydroxydimethylarsine oxide' OR 'dimethylarsenic acid' OR chexmate OR arsan OR 75-60-5 [rn] OR phytoestrogen* OR phytoestrogen*) AND (breast OR mammar* OR uterus OR uterine OR endometr* OR thyroid OR 'thyroid extract' OR 'thyroid usp' OR 'thyroid tablets' OR 8028-36-2 [rn] OR goitre OR goiter OR leiomyoma* or fibroid*) AND 1985:2014 [yr] AND (eng [la]) NOT PubMed [org] NOT PubDart [org]	

Table 14: Details of search strings used for literature searches in support of review sub-questions 1 and 2—search strings for www.clinicaltrials.gov

Set number	Search	Commentary
2	(OROBOL OR DAIDZIN OR GENISTIN OR GLYCITIN OR PUERARIN OR EQUOL OR DIHYDRODAIDZEIN OR DESMETHYLANGOLENSIN OR DMA OR PHYTOESTROGEN OR PHYTOOESTROGEN) AND (breast OR mammar OR thyroid OR uterus OR uterine OR endometrial OR endometrium OR goitre OR goiter OR leiomyoma OR fibroid OR fibroids)	
1	(isoflavones OR KUDZU OR SOY OR SOYBEAN OR PUERARIA OR DAIDZEIN OR GENISTEIN OR FORMONONETIN OR BIOCHANIN OR IRILONE OR GLYCITEIN OR PRUNETIN OR PRATENSEIN OR PSEUDOBAPTIGENIN OR CALYCOSIN) AND (breast OR mammar OR thyroid OR uterus OR uterine OR endometrial OR endometrium OR goitre OR goiter OR leiomyoma OR fibroid OR fibroids)	44 records downloaded

Table 15: Details of search strings used for literature searches in support of review sub-question 3— search strings for Web of Science Core Collection

Set number	Search	Commentary
8	((#5 NOT (#6 OR #7))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
7	((DT=review NOT (TS=meta-analysis OR DT=meta-analysis OR TS=(systematic near/2 review)))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
6	((Ts=(vicia faba or drosophila or 'allium cepa' or 'v faba' or onions or fish or fishes))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
5	((#3 NOT #4)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
4	((DT= (Addresses OR Case Reports OR Dictionary OR Directory OR Editorial OR Historical Article OR Interview OR Letter OR News OR Newspaper Article))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
3	(#2 AND #1) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
2	((TS=(genotox* OR mutagenicity OR 'genetic toxicity' OR (dna near/3 damage?) OR (dna near/4 injur*) OR (chromosome near/4 defect*) or mutagen* OR (chromosome* near/4 aberration?) or (gene* near/3 mutation?) or 'bacterial reverse' or ames or 'salmonella Typhimurium' or 's Typhimurium' OR 'e coli' OR 'Escherichia coli' or L5178Y or 'mouse lymphoma' OR cho Or 'Chinese hamster ovary' or v59 or 'Chinese hamster' or tk6 OR 'human lymphoblast*' or hprt OR xprt OR mla OR 'erythrocyte micronuclei' or transgenic Or comet or 'peripheral blood' OR 'bone marrow' or 'micronucleus test?' or 'sister chromatid exchange' OR 'unscheduled dna synthesis' or 'transformation assay?' or (aberration? Near/3 test*) or 'rodent dominant lethal test?' or uds))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
1	((TI=(ISOFLAVONES OR 'RED CLOVER' OR KUDZU OR SOY OR SOYBEAN OR SOYBEANS OR PUERARIA OR DAIDZEIN OR GENISTEIN OR FORMONONETIN OR 'BIOCHANIN A' OR IRLONE OR GLYCITEIN OR PRUNETIN OR PRATENSEIN OR PSEUDOBAPTIGENIN OR CALYCOSIN OR OROBOL OR DAIDZIN OR GENISTIN OR GLYCITIN OR PUERARIN OR 'S EQUOL' OR DIHYDRODAIDZEIN OR 'O DESMETHYLANGOLENSIN' OR 'O DMA' OR PHYTOESTROGEN? OR PHYTOOESTROGEN?))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	

Table 16: Details of search strings used for literature searches in support of review sub-question 4— search strings for MEDLINE

Set number	Search	Commentary
11	((#10 NOT #9)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
10	(#8) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
9	(#8) AND LANGUAGE: (English) AND DOCUMENT TYPES: (Review) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
8	((#7 AND #4)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
7	((#5 OR #6)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
6	((TS=((estrogen near/4 receptor?) OR (oestrogen near/4 receptor?) OR (hormone near/4 receptor?) mcf7 OR mcf 7 OR t47d OR steroidogenesis OR TG455 OR TG 455 OR TG456 OR TG 456 OR TG457 OR TG 457 OR (uterotrophic near/4 assay*) OR (uterotrophic near/4 test*) OR hershberger OR thyroid peroxidase OR iodide peroxidase OR thyroid hormone receptor? OR thyroxine receptor? or aromatase))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
5	((Mh:exp=(receptors, estrogen OR mcf-7 cells or receptors, thyroid hormone OR aromatase OR Aromatase Inhibitors))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
4	((#3 OR #2 OR #1)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	

Set number	Search	Commentary
3	((MH:EXP=(SOYBEANS OR MEDICAGO SATIVA OR TRIFOLIUM)))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
2	((Rn=(486-66-8 Or 446-72-0 OR 485-72-3 OR 491-80-5 OR 41653-81-0 OR 40957-83-3 OR 552-59-0 OR 2284-31-3 OR 90-29-9 OR 20575-57-9 OR 480-23-9 OR 552-66-9 OR 529-59-9 OR 40246-10-4 OR 3681-99-0 OR 531-95-3 OR 17238-05-0 OR 21255-69-6)))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
1	((TI= (ISOFLAVONES OR 'RED CLOVER' OR KUDZU OR SOY OR SOYBEAN OR SOYBEANS OR PUERARIA OR DAIDZEIN OR GENISTEIN OR FORMONONETIN OR 'BIOCHANIN A' OR IRILONE OR GLYCITEIN OR PRUNETIN OR PRATENSEIN OR PSEUDOBAPTIGENIN OR CALYCOSIN OR OROBOL OR DAIDZIN OR GENISTIN OR GLYCITIN OR PUERARIN OR 'S EQUOL' OR DIHYDRODAIDZEIN OR 'O DESMETHYLANGOLENSIN' OR 'O DMA' OR PHYTOESTROGEN? OR PHYTOOESTROGEN?)))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	

Table 17: Details of search strings used for literature searches in support of review sub-questions 6 and 7—search strings for MEDLINE

Set number	Search	Commentary
11	((#10 NOT #9)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
10	(#8) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
9	(#8) AND LANGUAGE: (English) AND DOCUMENT TYPES: (Review) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
8	((#7 AND #4)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
7	((#5 OR #6)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
6	((TS=((estrogen near/4 receptor?) OR (oestrogen near/4 receptor?) OR (hormone near/4 receptor?) mcf7 OR mcf 7 OR t47d OR steroidogenesis OR TG455 OR TG 455 OR TG456 OR TG 456 OR TG457 OR TG 457 OR (uterotrophic near/4 assay*) OR (uterotrophic near/4 test*) OR hershberger OR thyroid peroxidase OR iodide peroxidase OR thyroid hormone receptor? OR thyroxine receptor? or aromatase)))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
5	((Mh:exp=(receptors, estrogen OR mcf-7 cells or receptors, thyroid hormone OR aromatase OR Aromatase Inhibitors)))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
4	((#3 OR #2 OR #1)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
3	((MH:EXP=(SOYBEANS OR MEDICAGO SATIVA OR TRIFOLIUM)))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
2	((Rn=(486-66-8 Or 446-72-0 OR 485-72-3 OR 491-80-5 OR 41653-81-0 OR 40957-83-3 OR 552-59-0 OR 2284-31-3 OR 90-29-9 OR 20575-57-9 OR 480-23-9 OR 552-66-9 OR 529-59-9 OR 40246-10-4 OR 3681-99-0 OR 531-95-3 OR 17238-05-0 OR 21255-69-6)))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	
1	((TI= (ISOFLAVONES OR 'RED CLOVER' OR KUDZU OR SOY OR SOYBEAN OR SOYBEANS OR PUERARIA OR DAIDZEIN OR GENISTEIN OR FORMONONETIN OR 'BIOCHANIN A' OR IRILONE OR GLYCITEIN OR PRUNETIN OR PRATENSEIN OR PSEUDOBAPTIGENIN OR CALYCOSIN OR OROBOL OR DAIDZIN OR GENISTIN OR GLYCITIN OR PUERARIN OR 'S EQUOL' OR DIHYDRODAIDZEIN OR 'O DESMETHYLANGOLENSIN' OR 'O DMA' OR PHYTOESTROGEN? OR PHYTOOESTROGEN?)))) AND LANGUAGE: (English) DocType=All document types; Language=All languages;	

3.3. Study selection process

The whole selection process will be performed with DistillerSR. Studies to be included in the review will be selected using a two-step selection procedure:

- 1) **Screening of title and abstract** to identify potentially relevant studies that will be included for full-text screening, applying the selection criteria described in section 3.1. If the information contained in the title or abstract is not relevant to the research objectives, the article is not selected for full-text assessment. During the screening process, studies will be categorised into two groups corresponding to the two sub-questions that are the objectives of this review (i.e. humans and animal studies).

For sub-questions 1 and 2, if the title and/or abstract make clear that the main target organs (mammary gland, uterus, thyroid) were not the subject of the investigation, but the words 'adverse effects' or 'side effects' were mentioned (irrespective of whether there were effects or not), the paper is included to check if these effects had any relation to the target organs. In the case of doubt, the article will be included in full-text screening.

Articles that will be excluded during screening of the title and abstract will be stored in DistillerSR.

For sub-questions 1 and 2, this step will be conducted by EFSA staff, in duplicate. If there are doubts or divergences between the two reviewers, the full article will be screened.

- 2) **Screening of full text** to assess if the article is relevant to the risk assessment.

For sub-questions 1 and 2, this step will be conducted by EFSA staff, in duplicate, for the references retrieved. Possible divergences will be discussed by the whole Working Group, in case these would highlight the need for amendments to the inclusion/exclusion criteria. The content of the full text will be checked against the inclusion and exclusion criteria established in the protocol.

Possible divergences or doubt for inclusion will be discussed together with the relevant expert from the Working Group, in case these would highlight the need for amendments to the inclusion/exclusion criteria.

Articles reporting solely on ADME, i.e. without reporting on the main target organs, will not be included in this research question but will be flagged for the sub-questions on ADME.

For sub-question 3, both steps will be conducted by one expert from the Working Group.

For sub-question 4, both steps will be shared between two experts from the Working Group.

Screeners will be trained using written documentation on study eligibility. Eligibility criteria will be pilot tested on a subset of records, and refined if prone to misinterpretation. The results of the different phases of the study selection process will be reported in a flowchart as recommended in the PRISMA statement on preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (Moher et al., 2009).

3.4. Systematic review process for sub-questions 1 and 2

According to the systematic review process, the studies that will be considered eligible for inclusion will undergo data extraction and pre-defined information will be retrieved to allow an appraisal of their reliability.

3.4.1. Data extraction from included studies

Pre-defined data extraction forms (see Tables 18 and 19) will be used for collecting the data from the studies included in the review.

Data extracted will also be translated, whenever possible, into pre-defined codes (e.g. harmonised units of measurement) to allow subsequent data analysis.

Table 18: Data extraction for human studies

Ref ID	Authors, year	
Study characteristics and population	Study design	
	N	N allocated to treatment (N soy protein; N placebo) N included in the analysis (N soy protein; N placebo)
	Location	
	Sampling time frame	
	Menopausal status	
	Age at baseline	
	Age at menopause	
	Time since menopause	
	Inclusion criteria	
	Exclusion criteria	
	Funding source	
	Authors conflicts of interest	
Intervention/exposure	Clinical trial registration and/or acronym	
	Intervention	
Statistical analysis	Duration	
	Statistical analysis	
Results	Target organ 1	
	Endpoint 1	
	Target organ 2	
	Endpoint 2	

Table 19: Data extraction form for animal studies

Ref ID	Authors, year	
Animal model	Species	
	Strain (source)	
	Number of animals	
	Age (weight)	
	Diet	
	Dosing method	
	Funding source	
	Authors' conflicts of interest	
Dosing	Intervention	
Dosing	Start of intervention since ovariectomy	
	Duration	
Statistical analysis	Statistical analysis	
Results	Target organ 1	
	Endpoint 1	
	Endpoint 2	
	Target organ 2	
	Endpoint 3	

The data extraction forms will be pilot tested in a subset of studies. The data extraction form will be uploaded into the software DistillerSR and data extraction will be performed by EFSA staff.

Clear instructions for extracting data will be made available to data extractors.

In the case of missing or ambiguous data, a decision will be taken by the Working Group on whether to include or exclude the study.

3.4.2. Exclusion of studies of low reliability

A minimum level of reliability is deemed necessary for a study to be further considered for risk assessment. Human and animal studies must therefore be rated as 'definitely appropriate' or 'possibly appropriate' for the following elements:

- Is the characterisation and duration of the intervention/exposure appropriate for the endpoint of interest?
- Is the study duration appropriate for the endpoint of interest?
- Is the intervention/exposure of each study appropriately characterised?

For both human and animal studies, the intervention/exposure of each study must be characterised in terms of the dose of total isoflavones (in the case of mixtures from natural extract) or the dose of the individual isoflavones (when composition of the mixture is further specified or in the case of a single isoflavone being administered) and the total dosage administered.

Regarding the duration of the intervention, a minimum of 3 months is deemed necessary for a human study to be considered relevant to the risk assessment, considering the fact that consumption of food supplements containing isolated isoflavones by peri- and post-menopausal women is expected to last for longer periods. For animal studies, a minimum duration of treatment of at least 5 days will be considered.

The appropriateness of the study duration will instead be judged in relation to the endpoints of interest. For cancer incidence/mortality in human studies, only studies with a follow-up of at least 12 months will be considered. For animal studies in which a known carcinogen is administered to animals, a minimum duration of 3 months is deemed appropriate, whereas duration of at least 12 months is needed for studies without concomitant administration of the carcinogen agent.

For thyroid endpoints (excluding cancer) and for all the other surrogate endpoints (see Table 3), studies of any duration will be considered appropriate.

Studies that are considered of sufficient reliability will be further appraised for internal validity (risk of bias) and precision. Those deemed not appropriate will be excluded from data extraction and subsequent reliability assessment.

3.4.3. Assessment of reliability of included studies

The human studies to be considered for risk assessment will be sorted by:

- target organ addressed (mammary gland, uterus, thyroid);
- endpoint(s) measured (see Table 3);
- isoflavones administered (extracts containing mixtures of isoflavones, individual isoflavones, mixtures of isoflavones in combination with other substances);
- study design.

The animal studies included will be grouped by:

- animal species;
- target organ addressed (mammary gland, uterus, thyroid);
- endpoint(s) measured (see Table 3);
- isoflavones administered (extracts containing mixtures of isoflavones, individual isoflavones, mixtures of isoflavones in combination with other substances);
- duration (e.g. short-term toxicity, long-term toxicity and carcinogenicity).

The reliability of all studies included in the assessment will be appraised by considering the following dimensions:

- Internal validity (or risk of bias), defined as 'the extent to which the design and conduct of a study are likely to have prevented bias', i.e. non-random error (Higgins and Green, 2011).
- Precision, defined as the extent to which a study is capable of providing results free from random error (reflected by the size of the confidence interval around the estimate).

The elements that will be considered for appraising the reliability of each individual study are illustrated in the critical appraisal tool reported in Appendix A. The tool was adapted from the National Toxicology Program, Office of Health Assessment and Translation's Risk of Bias tool (NTP OHAT, online). The tool will be uploaded in Distiller to allow web-based appraisal of the studies. Each study will be appraised independently by two reviewers (experts from the Working Group) and possible discrepancies will be discussed by the whole Working Group.

For each element considered in the appraisal, experts' judgement will be translated into the rating scale shown in Table 20.

Table 20: Proposed rating scale for appraising the studies

Rating	Internal validity	Precision
++	Definitively low risk of bias	Definitively appropriate
+	Probably low risk of bias	Probably appropriate
-	Probably high risk of bias	Probably not appropriate
--	Definitively high risk of bias	Definitively not appropriate
NA	Not applicable	Not applicable

Allocation of studies to different tiers of reliability

For each target organ and its associated endpoints, studies will be assigned to 'tiers of reliability', along with clear explanation for their allocation, according to their study design and the isoflavones used. This will then be considered in the analysis (see section 3.6).

For the purpose of creating a classification of the reliability of the evidence, two key questions have been identified among the elements that need to be considered for the appraisal of internal validity of the studies.

Human studies

The two key questions for human studies are the following:

- Did the study design or analysis account for important confounding or modifying variables?
- Can we be confident in the outcome assessment?

Each study will be described as '1st tier', '2nd tier' or '3rd tier' for reliability using the method described below.

A human study is classified in the 1st tier if:

- it is rated as 'definitely low' or 'probably low' for the two questions A and B (see Appendix A);

AND

- at least half of the other applicable questions are answered 'definitely low' or 'probably low' regarding risk of bias.

A study is classified in the 3rd tier if:

- it is rated as 'definitely high' or 'probably high' for the two questions A and B (see Appendix A);

AND

- at least half of the other applicable questions are answered 'definitely high' or 'probably high' regarding risk of bias.

A study is classified in the 2nd tier if it does not fall in the 1st or 3rd tier.

Animal studies

The three key questions for animal studies are the following:

- A. Did the study design or analysis account for important confounding or modifying variables?
- B. Can we be confident in the outcome assessment?
- C. Are the repeated measurements (if any) on the experimental units treated appropriately?

Each study will be described as '1st tier', '2nd tier' or '3rd tier' for reliability using the method described below.

An animal study is classified in the 1st tier if:

- it is rated as 'definitely low' or 'probably low' for the three questions A–C (see Appendix A);

AND

- at least half of the other applicable questions are answered 'definitely low' or 'probably low' regarding risk of bias.

A study is classified in the 3rd tier if:

- it is rated as 'definitely high' or 'probably high' for two out of the three questions A–C (see Appendix A);

AND

- at least half of the other applicable questions are answered 'definitely high' or 'probably high' regarding risk of bias.

A study is classified in the 2nd tier if it does not fall in the 1st or 3rd tier.

3.5. Narrative review process for answering risk assessment sub-questions 3 and 4

The included studies will be screened for relevance, appraised and synthesised by the relevant domain experts.

3.6. Analysis of data

Owing to the expected large heterogeneity of the available evidence, it is anticipated that a qualitative analysis will be performed.

Each study considered for inclusion will be summarised in tabular format.

3.7. Presentation of the results

For human and animal studies considered for sub-questions 1 and 2, the results will be grouped according to:

- type of exposure/intervention;
- target organ;
- endpoint(s);
- study design;
- tiers of reliability.

The results will be presented taking into consideration the abovementioned elements and any additional aspect that the Working Group may identify as relevant at a later stage.

Hazard identification conclusions will be drawn considering the reliability of the studies, the consistency of the reported results across the different studies, their biological plausibility, etc., and expressing uncertainties.

4. Methods for performing hazard characterisation

If it can be concluded that isolated isoflavones may increase the incidence of cancer in the mammary gland/uterus/thyroid or effects in the three organs in experimental animals or humans and the mode of action is identified as being non-genotoxic, a dose–response relationship will be established. The aim of the dose–response assessment is the identification of a point of departure such as the no observed adverse effect level, the lowest observed adverse effect level or the lower confidence limit of the benchmark dose.

If data allow, dose–response modelling will be performed with animal data, and the lower 95 % confidence interval of the dose eliciting a 10 % increase in tumour incidence compared with the incidence in control animals will be taken as the point of departure. This point of departure will be used for deriving an endpoint-specific value (EPSV). Using human data, the dose–response modelling performed in the studies will be critically assessed to identify the dose at which a significant increase in tumour incidence is observed, which will form a basis for identifying the point of departure for deriving an EPSV⁵ (EFSA, 2009). The same applies for all the thyroid endpoints, as well as for all the other surrogate endpoints considered in this risk assessment.

4.1. Review and analysis of ADME data

In this step, a narrative review of the available evidence will be performed by two Working Group experts with the aim of defining differences related to inter-species toxicokinetics, including inter-individual variability, that need to be taken into account for the safety factors to be applied when establishing an EPSV.

Details of the literature search, to be performed on Web of Science, are shown in Table 21.

Table 21: Details of search strings used for literature searches in support of review sub-questions 5, 6 and 7—search strings for Web of Science including MEDLINE

Set number	Search	Number of hits (30.01.2015)
6	#5 AND #4 Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=All years	168
5	(DT=review OR TS=meta-analysis OR DT=meta-analysis OR TS=(systematic near/2 review)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=All years	1 632 098
4	#3 OR #2 OR #1 Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=All years	4 989
3	(TI=(ISOFLAVONES OR DAIDZEIN OR GENISTEIN OR FORMONONETIN OR BIOCHANIN OR IRILONE OR GLYCITEIN OR PRUNETIN OR PRATENSEIN OR PSEUDOBAPTIGENIN OR CALYCOSIN OR OROBOL OR DAIDZIN OR GENISTIN OR GLYCITIN OR PUERARIN OR EQUO OR DIHYDRODAIDZEIN OR DESMETHYLANGOLENSI OR DMA OR PHYTOESTROGEN? OR PHYTOOESTROGEN?) AND TI=(adme or metaboli* or absorption or absorbed or bioavailability or biotransform\$ or pharmacokinetic\$ or concentration\$)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=All years	528
2	Rn=(486-66-8 Or 446-72-0 OR 485-72-3 OR 491-80-5 OR 41653-81-0 OR 40957-83-3 OR 552-59-0 OR 2284-31-3 OR 90-29-9 OR 20575-57-9 OR 480-23-9 OR 552-66-9 OR 529-59-9 OR 40246-10-4 OR 3681-99-0 OR 531-95-3 OR 17238-05-0 OR 21255-69-6) AND (mh:exp=metabolism OR mh:exp=biotransformation OR mh:exp=pharmacokinetics)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=All years	108
1	(MH:exp=isoflavones AND (mh:exp=metabolism OR mh:exp=biotransformation OR mh:exp=pharmacokinetics)) AND LANGUAGE: (English) Indexes=MEDLINE Timespan=All years	4 666

⁵ HBGVs developed for substances found in food and drinking water are the quantitative expression of the range of oral exposure (either acute or chronic) that would be expected to be without appreciable health risk. An EPSV is an analogous term describing the quantitative oral exposure that would be expected to be without appreciable risk for that specific endpoint but not all endpoints.

4.2. Review and analysis of mode of action data

Depending on the association found between isoflavones and the endpoints considered, an analysis of the relevant data will be performed to identify potential mode(s) of action. The results concerning genotoxicity and results from *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies on the endocrine activities and/or other mechanistic data will be assessed.

Potential modes of action will be assessed in line with the IPCS Mode of Action Framework (Boobis et al., 2006).

4.3. Method for performing exposure assessment

In order to perform an assessment of the exposure, a request for information has been sent to the relevant food sector associations, requesting that data be submitted on the typical composition of food supplements targeted at peri- and post-menopausal women.

In particular, relevant food sector associations have been asked to submit:

- technical data on the specifications of the preparations used, on their quantitative/chemical composition and on the stability of isoflavones in food supplements; and
- the range of recommended number of daily servings of food supplements, as suggested on the labels of the food/dietary supplements.

The data received will be analysed by EFSA to estimate mean and maximum exposure levels in peri- and post-menopausal women. The exposure will be estimated for at least total isoflavones, whereas exposure estimates for the individual substances will be calculated only in cases where information on their levels in food supplements are made available to EFSA.

Previous opinions on botanical preparations used in food supplements (EFSA ANS Panel, 2013a, b) have shown that there may be significant discrepancies between the amount claimed on the label of the products and the concentration determined analytically. To this end, results obtained from the industry will be cross-checked with data available in the public literature.

A 'baseline' value on the average exposure to isoflavones from the diet in the specific population will be retrieved in the published literature.

Finally, the estimated intake of isoflavones from food supplements will be compared with a 'baseline' value on the average exposure to isoflavones from the diet in the specific population.

5. Uncertainty analysis

Efforts will be made to assess, in a qualitative way, the impact of the individual sources of uncertainty on the final outcome and, possibly, the combined impact of multiple uncertainties.

6. Approach for reaching risk characterisation conclusions

6.1. Animal data

If the ESPV is based on animal data, the conventional default assessment factor of 100 could be modified depending on the result of the assessment of *in vivo* kinetic and dynamic data aiming to establish a difference between humans and animals.

6.2. Human data

If the EPSV is based on human data, the default chemical specific assessment factor of 3.16 for kinetic and dynamic variability could be modified, depending on the result of an assessment of *in vivo* kinetic and dynamic data on variability of these between humans. Because human data is used, no inter-species extrapolation factor has to be applied. Furthermore, owing to the exclusion and inclusion criteria applied to the literature search and to the selection process that follows, the study population is specifically selected to represent the population of interest, namely peri- and post-menopausal women. As this is considered the sensitive population, consideration of lowering the value of the dynamic chemical specific assessment factor of 3.16 may be justified. Hence, the assessment factor to

account for intra-species variability is covered by basing the EPSV on the results of studies in the specific population of interest.

The resulting EPSV will be compared with estimates of exposure to isoflavones from the intake of food supplements and will be used to consider whether the intake levels, with respect to the specific endpoints in the target population, are safe.

If the data suggest that the substances are carcinogenic and genotoxicity will be established as the mode of action, an EPSV will not be derived and instead the margin of exposure approach will be followed (EFSA, 2005).

7. Plans for updating the literature searches and dealing with newly available evidence

The literature searches performed as detailed in section 3.2 will be repeated approximately 3 months before the planned date of adoption of the opinion (currently expected before the end of September 2015).

The papers retrieved by these additional searches will be screened for relevance, applying the same criteria.

Relevant studies will be narratively reviewed by the Working Group experts and where controversial issues are identified (e.g. conflicting conclusions) these will be discussed in the Working Group, which will prepare a proposal on how to deal with the issues. The controversial issues and the proposed solution will be brought to the attention of the Panel, which will take the final decision.

8. Human resources, software and timelines for performing risk assessment

Tasks for performing hazard identification will be allocated among Working Group experts, as shown in Table 22.

Provisional deadlines are given below in Table 22, subject to changes depending on the volume of data retrieved.

Table 22: Task allocation for performing assessment

What	Who	Software	By when (planned)
Hazard identification			
Search process	Working Group expert	Endnote	End of September 2014
Study selection for relevance for sub-questions 1 and 2	1 EFSA staff member	DistillerSR	Mid-October 2014
Referee in case of doubt or divergences	All Working Group members		Mid-October 2014
Data extraction sub-question 1	1 EFSA staff	DistillerSR	End of November 2014
Appraisal of RoB sub-question 1	2 experts from the Working Group	DistillerSR	End of December 2014
Data extraction sub-question 2	1 EFSA staff	DistillerSR	End of November 2014
Appraisal of RoB sub-question 2	2 experts from the Working Group	DistillerSR	End of December 2014
Study selection for relevance and narrative review of sub-question 3	Working Group expert	DistillerSR	End of January 2015
Study selection for relevance and narrative review of sub-question 4	2 experts from the Working Group		Study selection for relevance and narrative review of sub-question 4

What	Who	Software	By when (planned)
Analysis of data including expression of uncertainty and presentation of results	All Working Group members	n.a.	End of February 2015
Hazard characterisation			
Review and analysis of ADME data	2 experts from the Working Group	n.a.	End of March 2015
Review and analysis of mode of action data	2 experts from the Working Group	n.a.	End of March 2015
Exposure assessment			
Compilation of data received by food sector industry	EFSA staff	n.a.	End of March 2015
Literature check for background data on dietary exposure to isoflavones	EFSA staff	EndNote	End of March 2015
Estimation of exposure scenarios	EFSA staff	EFSA Global Consumption database	End of March 2015
Plans for updating literature searches			
Update the searches	Working Group expert	Endnote	End of June 2015
Select studies for relevance	1 EFSA staff	DistillerSR	Mid-July 2015
Narrative review of relevant additional studies retrieved	All Working Group members	/	End of August 2015
Finalisation of the opinion: end of September 2015			

9. History of the amendments

This protocol was agreed as the final version by the Working Group on 16 September 2014.

During the implementation of the protocol, the following amendments were introduced:

Sections 3.4.1 and 8: The data extraction forms presented in Tables 18 and 19 are the final forms used for extracting and presenting the data. The data extraction forms were not uploaded into the software DistillerSR but were performed manually by EFSA staff.

Section 3.4.2: In order to exclude transient effects associated with short-term supplementation with isoflavones, the Panel agreed that a minimum duration of 12 weeks or 3 months should be used for inclusion of human intervention studies in the current assessment. For similar reasons, a minimum duration of 5 days was used for animal studies, which was an intermediate cut-off point between the minimum recommended duration of 3 days for the test in ovariectomised animals and the minimum recommended duration of 7 days for weak oestrogens in accordance with the uterotrophic bioassay in rodents (OECD, 2007).

Animal studies conducted on special models such as athymic ovariectomised mice implanted with cells from breast cancer cell lines, or studies on mammary gland carcinogenesis induced in rodents with well-known carcinogens were flagged in Distiller as potentially useful in hazard identification and for developing a mode of action analysis, but were excluded from the systematic review.

Section 3.4.3: On 29 January 2015, the rules for assigning tiers of reliability for human and animal studies were amended. The changes were introduced in the Distiller tool after an initial test performed by the experts on a subset of studies. The rules presented in the current version of the protocol are those applied in the systematic review.

Section 3.4.3: The final data did not allow the grouping of the animal studies by duration; instead, this parameter was considered for the presentation of the studies in tables (by descending order, i.e. from the longest duration to the shortest).

Sections 7 and 8: On 8 May 2015, it was agreed by the Working Group that only one update of the literature searches would be performed instead of the two initially planned in a previous version of the protocol. Moreover, the additional studies retrieved were included in the systematic review and appraised as the others.

Section 8: Data extraction was performed manually, after studies were already appraised for their reliability.

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Abbreviations

ADME	absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion
ANS	EFSA Panel on Food Additives and Nutrient Sources added to Food
BfR	Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EPSV	endpoint-specific value
fT ₃	free triiodothyronine
fT ₄	free thyroxine
FMP	final menstrual period
HBGV	health-based guidance value
NDA	EFSA Panel on Dietetic Products, Nutrition and Allergies
NTP	National Toxicology Program
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OHAT	Office of Health Assessment and Translation
T ₃	triiodothyronine
T ₄	thyroxine
TSH	thyroid-stimulating hormone
WHO	World Health Organization

Appendix A – Critical appraisal tools for human and animal studies

A1. Appraisal tool for human intervention studies (adapted from NTP OHT, online)

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
1	Bias domain: selection bias	++	Acceptable methods of randomisation include: referring to a random number table, using a computer random number generator, coin tossing, shuffling cards or envelopes, throwing dice or drawing of lots (Higgins and Green, 2011). Restricted randomisation (e.g. blocked randomisation) to ensure particular allocation ratios will be considered to have a low risk of bias. Similarly, stratified randomisation and minimisation approaches that attempt to minimise imbalance between groups on important prognostic factors (e.g. age) will be considered acceptable
		+	There is indirect evidence that subjects were allocated to study groups using a method with a random component (i.e. authors state that allocation was random, without description of the method used) OR it is deemed that allocation without a clearly random component during the study would not appreciably bias results. For example, approaches such as biased coin or urn randomisation, replacement randomisation, mixed randomisation and maximal randomisation may require consultation with a statistician to determine risk of bias rating (Higgins and Green, 2011)
		–	There is indirect evidence that subjects were allocated to study groups using a method with a non-random component OR there is insufficient information provided about how subjects were allocated to study groups. Non-random allocation methods may be systematic, but have the potential to allow participants or researchers to anticipate the allocation to study groups. Such 'quasi-random' methods include alternation, assignment based on date of birth, case record number or date of presentation to study (Higgins and Green, 2011)
		—	There is direct evidence that subjects were allocated to study groups using a non-random method including judgement of the clinician, preference of the participant, the results of a laboratory test or a series of tests, or availability of the intervention (Higgins and Green, 2011)
		NA	Not applicable
2	Was allocation to study groups adequately concealed? <i>Note: (1) a question under performance bias addresses blinding of personnel and human subjects to treatment during the study; (2) a question under detection bias addresses blinding of outcome assessors.</i>	++	There is direct evidence that at the time of recruitment the research personnel and subjects did not know which study group subjects were allocated to, and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding of allocation until after recruitment was complete and irrevocable. Methods used to ensure allocation concealment include central allocation (including telephone, web-based and pharmacy-controlled randomisation); sequentially numbered drug containers of identical appearance; sequentially numbered, opaque, sealed envelopes; or equivalent methods
		+	There is indirect evidence that the research personnel and subjects did not know which study group subjects were allocated to OR it is deemed that lack of adequate allocation concealment would not appreciably bias results
	Allocation concealment requires that research personnel do not know which administered dose		

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
	or exposure level is assigned at the start of a study. Human studies also require that allocation be concealed from human subjects prior to entering the study	–	There is indirect evidence that at the time of recruitment it was possible for the research personnel and subjects to know which study group subjects were allocated to, or it is likely that they could have broken the blinding of allocation before recruitment was complete and irrevocable OR there is insufficient information provided about allocation to study groups. <i>Note: inadequate methods include using an open random allocation schedule (e.g. a list of random numbers), assignment envelopes used without appropriate safeguards (e.g. if envelopes were unsealed or non-opaque or not sequentially numbered), alternation or rotation; date of birth; case record number; or any other explicitly unconcealed procedure. For example, if the use of assignment envelopes is described, but it remains unclear whether envelopes were sequentially numbered, opaque and sealed</i>
		—	There is direct evidence that at the time of recruitment it was possible for the research personnel and subjects to know which study group subjects were allocated to, or it is likely that they could have broken the blinding of allocation before recruitment was complete and irrevocable
		NA	Not applicable
Bias domain: confounding bias			
3	Key question A: Did the study design or analysis account for important confounding and modifying variables and were confounding variables assessed consistently across groups using valid and reliable measures? Interpretation of study findings may be distorted by failure to consider the extent to which systematic differences in baseline characteristics risk factors, prognostic variables or co-occurring exposures among comparison groups may reduce or increase the observed effect. Lack of consideration of confounding factors can also influence the variability of the estimates. Appropriate methods to account for these differences would include multivariable analysis, stratification, matching of cases and controls or other approaches. Examples: age, socio-demographic status, smoking, body mass index	++	There is direct evidence that appropriate adjustments or explicit considerations were made for primary covariates and confounders in the final analyses through the use of statistical models to reduce research-specific bias including standardisation, case matching, adjustment in multivariate model, stratification, propensity scoring or other methods were appropriately justified. Acceptable consideration of appropriate adjustment factors includes cases when the factor is not included in the final adjustment model because the author conducted analyses that indicated it did not need to be included. There is direct evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using valid and reliable measurements
		+	There is indirect evidence that appropriate adjustments were made for most primary covariates and confounders and that they were assessed using valid and reliable measurements OR it is deemed that the measures used would not appreciably bias results (i.e. the authors justified the validity of the measures from previously published research) and that not considering or only considering a partial list of covariates or confounders in the final analyses would not appreciably bias results
		–	There is indirect evidence that the distribution of primary covariates and known confounders differed between the groups and was not appropriately adjusted for in the final analyses and that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using measurements of unknown validity OR there is insufficient information provided about the distribution of known confounders and about the measures used to assess primary covariates and confounders
		—	There is direct evidence that the distribution of primary covariates and known confounders differed between the groups, confounding was demonstrated, and was not appropriately adjusted for in the final analyses and that they were assessed using non valid measurements
		NA	Not applicable
4	Did researchers adjust or control for other exposures that are anticipated to bias results? Examples: background diet (e.g. vegan/vegetarian status, phytoestrogen content of the diet), baseline isoflavones	++	There is direct evidence that other exposures anticipated to bias results were not present or were appropriately adjusted for
		+	There is indirect evidence that other co-exposures anticipated to bias results were not present or were appropriately adjusted for OR it is deemed that co-exposures present would not appreciably bias results. Note, as discussed above, this includes insufficient information provided on co-exposures in general population studies

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
	intake from diet, concomitant medication (e.g. antibiotic use, use of hormone replacement therapy), reproductive hormonal factors (e.g. number of children, breast feeding)	–	There is indirect evidence that the control group may have received the treatment OR there was an unbalanced provision of additional co-exposures which was not appropriately adjusted for
		—	There is direct evidence that the control group received the treatment or there was an unbalanced provision of additional co-exposures which was not appropriately adjusted for
		NA	Not applicable
Bias domain: performance bias			
5	Did deviations from the study protocol impact the results? <i>Note: it is recognised that protocol deviations are unlikely to be reported given reporting practices. However, in the long term, collecting this information may generate data that will allow us to empirically assess evidence of this bias</i>	++	There is direct evidence that there were no deviations from the protocol (i.e. the study report explicitly provides this level of detail)
		+	There is indirect evidence that there were no deviations from the protocol (i.e. authors did not report any deviations) OR deviations from the protocol are described and it is deemed that they would not appreciably bias results
		–	There is indirect evidence that there were large deviations from the protocol as outlined in the methods or study report
		—	There is direct evidence that there were large deviations from the protocol as outlined in the methods or study report
		NA	Not applicable
6	Were the research personnel and human subjects blinded to the study group during the study? Blinding requires that study scientists do not know which administered dose or exposure level the human subject is being given (i.e. study group). Human studies also require blinding of the human subjects when possible	++	There is direct evidence that the subjects and research personnel were adequately blinded to study group, and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding during the study. Methods used to ensure blinding include central allocation, sequentially numbered drug containers of identical appearance; sequentially numbered, opaque, sealed envelopes; or equivalent methods
		+	There is indirect evidence that the research personnel and subjects were adequately blinded to study group, and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding during the study OR it is deemed that lack of adequate blinding during the study would not appreciably bias results
		–	There is indirect evidence that it was possible for research personnel or subjects to infer the study group OR there is insufficient information provided about blinding of study group. Inadequate methods include using an open random allocation schedule (e.g. a list of random numbers), assignment envelopes used without appropriate safeguards (e.g. if envelopes were unsealed or non-opaque or not sequentially numbered), alternation or rotation; date of birth; case record number; or any other explicitly unconcealed procedure. For example, if the use of assignment envelopes is described, but it remains unclear whether envelopes were sequentially numbered, opaque and sealed
		—	There is direct evidence for lack of adequate blinding of the study group including no blinding or incomplete blinding of research personnel and subjects. For some treatments, such as behavioural interventions, allocation to study groups cannot be concealed
		NA	Not applicable

Bias domain: attrition/exclusion bias

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
7	<p>Were outcome data incomplete due to attrition or exclusion from analysis?</p> <p>Attrition rates are required to be similar and uniformly low across groups with respect to withdrawal or exclusion from analysis.</p> <p>When withdrawals or incomplete outcome are not similar and uniformly low across groups, a bias can be introduced in the estimates</p>	++	<p>There is direct evidence that there was no loss of subjects during the study and outcome data were complete</p> <p>OR loss of subjects (i.e. incomplete outcome data) was adequately addressed and reasons were documented when human subjects were removed from a study. Review authors should be confident that the participants included in the analysis are exactly those who were randomised into the trial. Acceptable handling of subject attrition includes very little missing outcome data (less than 10 % in each group (Genaidy et al., 2007)); reasons for missing subjects unlikely to be related to outcome (for survival data, censoring unlikely to be introducing bias); missing outcome data balanced in numbers across study groups, with similar reasons for missing data across groups</p> <p>OR analyses (such as intention-to-treat analysis) in which missing data have been imputed using appropriate methods (insuring that the characteristics of subjects lost to follow-up or with unavailable records are described in an identical way and are not significantly different from those of the study participants).</p> <p><i>Note: participants randomised but subsequently found not to be participants randomised but subsequently found not to be eligible need not always be considered as having missing outcome data</i></p>
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that loss of subjects (i.e. incomplete outcome data) was adequately addressed and reasons were documented when human subjects were removed from a study</p> <p>OR it is deemed that the proportion lost to follow-up would not appreciably bias results (less than 20 % in each group (Genaidy et al., 2007)). This would include reports of no statistical differences in characteristics of subjects lost to follow-up or with unavailable records from those of the study participants. Generally, the higher the ratio of participants with missing data to participants with events, the greater potential there is for bias. For studies with a long duration of follow-up, some withdrawals for such reasons are inevitable</p>
		–	<p>There is indirect evidence that loss of subjects (i.e. incomplete outcome data) was unacceptably large (greater than 20 % in each group (Genaidy et al., 2007)) and not adequately addressed</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about numbers of subjects lost to follow-up</p>
		—	<p>There is direct evidence that loss of subjects (i.e. incomplete outcome data) was unacceptably large and not adequately addressed. Unacceptable handling of subject attrition includes reason for missing outcome data likely to be related to true outcome, with either imbalance in numbers or reasons for missing data across study groups; or potentially inappropriate application of imputation</p>
		NA	Not applicable
Bias domain: information/detection bias			
8	<p>Were the outcome assessors blinded to study group or exposure level?</p> <p>Blinding requires that outcome assessors do not know the study group or exposure level of the human subject or animal when the outcome is assessed</p>	++	<p>There is direct evidence that the outcome assessors (including study subjects, if outcomes were self-reported) were adequately blinded to the study group, and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding prior to reporting outcomes</p>
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that the outcome assessors (including study subjects, if outcomes were self-reported) were adequately blinded to the study group, and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding prior to reporting outcomes</p> <p>OR it is deemed that lack of adequate blinding of outcome assessors would not appreciably bias results, which may vary by outcome (i.e. blinding is especially important for subjective measures)</p>
		–	<p>There is indirect evidence that it was possible for outcome assessors (including study subjects if outcomes were self-reported) to infer the study group prior to reporting outcomes</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about blinding of outcome assessors</p>

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
		—	There is direct evidence for lack of adequate blinding of outcome assessors (including study subjects if outcomes were self-reported), including no blinding or incomplete blinding
		NA	Not applicable
9	<p>Key question B: Can we be confident in the outcome assessment?</p> <p>Confidence requires valid, reliable and sensitive methods to assess the outcome and the methods should be applied consistently across groups</p>	++	There is direct evidence that the outcome was assessed using well-established methods, the 'gold standard', and subjects had been followed for the same length of time in all study groups. Acceptable assessment methods will depend on the outcome, but examples of such methods may include objectively measured with diagnostic methods, measured by trained interviewers, obtained from registries
		+	There is indirect evidence that the outcome was assessed using acceptable methods (i.e. deemed valid and reliable but not the gold standard) and subjects had been followed for the same length of time in all study groups OR it is deemed that the outcome assessment methods used would not appreciably bias results. Acceptable, but not ideal assessment methods will depend on the outcome, but examples of such methods may include proxy reporting of outcomes and mining of data collected for other purposes
		–	There is indirect evidence that the outcome assessment method is an insensitive instrument, the authors did not validate the methods used, or the length of follow up differed by study group OR there is insufficient information provided about validation of outcome assessment method
		—	There is direct evidence that the outcome assessment method is an insensitive instrument, or the length of follow-up differed by study group
		NA	Not applicable
Bias domain: selective reporting			
10	<p>Were all measured outcomes reported?</p> <p>Selective reporting bias refers to selective inclusion of outcomes in the publication of the study on the basis of the results.</p> <p>Selective reporting is present if pre-specified outcomes are not reported or incompletely reported. It is probably widespread and difficult to assess with confidence for most studies unless the study protocol is available. Selective reporting bias can be assessed by comparing the 'methods' and 'results' sections of the paper, and by considering outcomes measured in the context of knowledge in the field. Abstracts of presentations relating to the study may contain information about outcomes not subsequently mentioned in publications. Selective reporting bias should be suspected if the study does not report outcomes in the results section that would have been expected based on the methods, or if a composite</p>	++	There is direct evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (primary and secondary) outlined in the material and methods, abstract and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported. This would include outcomes reported with sufficient detail to be included in meta-analysis or fully tabulated during data extraction
		+	There is indirect evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (primary and secondary) outlined in the material and methods, abstract and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported OR analyses that had not been planned at the outset of the study (i.e. retrospective unplanned subgroup analyses) are clearly indicated as such and it is deemed that the omitted analyses were not appropriate and selective reporting would not appreciably bias results. This would include outcomes reported with insufficient detail such as only reporting that results were statistically significant (or not)
		–	There is indirect evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (primary and secondary) outlined in the material and methods, abstract and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported OR there is insufficient information provided about selective outcome reporting
		—	There is direct evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (primary and secondary) outlined in the material and methods, abstract and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have not been reported. In addition to not reporting outcomes, this would include reporting outcomes based on composite score without individual outcome components or outcomes reported using measurements, analysis methods or subsets of the data (e.g. subscales) that were not pre-specified or reporting outcomes not pre-specified (unless clear justification for their reporting is provided, such as an unexpected effect)

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
	score is present without the individual component outcomes. It may be useful to pay attention to author affiliations and funding source, which can contribute to selective outcome reporting when results are not consistent with expectations or value to the research objectives	NA	Not applicable

A2. Appraisal tool for human observational studies (adapted from NTP OHAT, online)

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
Bias domain: selection bias			
1	Were the comparison groups appropriate? Comparison group appropriateness refers to having similar baseline characteristics and recruited with the same method and inclusion/exclusion criteria between the groups aside from the exposures and outcomes under study	++	<p>There is direct evidence that subjects (both exposed and non-exposed) were similar (e.g. recruited from the same eligible population, recruited with the same method of ascertainment using the same inclusion and exclusion criteria, and were of similar age and health status), recruited within the same time frame, and had the similar participation/response rates.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is direct evidence that cases and controls were similar (e.g. recruited from the same eligible population including being of similar age, gender, ethnicity, and eligibility criteria other than outcome of interest as appropriate), recruited within the same time frame, and controls are described as having no history of the outcome.</p> <p><i>Note: a study will be considered low risk of bias if baseline characteristics of groups differed but these differences were considered as potential confounding or stratification variables</i></p>
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that subjects (both exposed and non-exposed) were similar (e.g. recruited from the same eligible population, recruited with the same method of ascertainment using the same inclusion and exclusion criteria, and were of similar age and health status), recruited within the same time frame, and had the similar participation/response rates</p> <p>OR differences between groups would not appreciably bias results.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is indirect evidence that cases and controls were similar (e.g. recruited from the same eligible population, recruited with the same method of ascertainment using the same inclusion and exclusion criteria, and were of similar age), recruited within the same time frame, and controls are described as having no history of the outcome</p> <p>OR differences between cases and controls would not appreciably bias results</p>
		-	<p>There is indirect evidence that subjects (both exposed and non-exposed) were not similar, recruited within very different time frames, or had the very different participation/response rates</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about the comparison group including a different rate of non-response without an explanation.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is direct evidence that controls were drawn from a very dissimilar population than cases or recruited within very different time frames</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about the appropriateness of controls including rate of response reported for cases only</p>

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
		—	There is direct evidence that subjects (both exposed and non-exposed) were not similar, recruited within very different time frames, or had very different participation/response rates. <u>For case-control studies:</u> There is direct evidence that controls were drawn from a very dissimilar population than cases or recruited within very different time frames
		NA	Not applicable
Bias domain: confounding bias			
2	<p>Key question A: Did the study design or analysis account for important confounding and modifying variables?</p> <p>Interpretation of study findings may be distorted by failure to consider the extent to which systematic differences in baseline characteristics risk factors, prognostic variables or co-occurring exposures among comparison groups may reduce or increase the observed effect. Appropriate methods to account for these differences would include multivariable analysis, stratification, matching of cases and controls or other approaches.</p> <p>Consistent application of valid, reliable, and sensitive methods of assessing important confounding or modifying variables is required across study groups.</p> <p>The requirement for assessing the confounding variables with valid and reliable measures is directly linked to the relative importance of the confounding variable considered under selection bias (i.e. independent of study design, if a confounder needed to be accounted for in design or analyses, then measurement of that variable had to be reliable).</p> <p>Examples: age, socio-demographic status, smoking, body mass index</p>	++	<p>There is direct evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using valid and reliable measurements and that appropriate adjustments or explicit considerations were made for primary covariates and confounders in the final analyses through the use of statistical models to reduce research-specific bias including standardisation, case matching, adjustment in multivariate model, stratification, propensity scoring or other methods were appropriately justified. Acceptable consideration of appropriate adjustment factors includes cases when the factor is not included in the final adjustment model because the author conducted analyses that indicated it did not need to be included.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is direct evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using valid and reliable measurements and that appropriate adjustments were made for primary covariates and confounders in the final analyses through the use of statistical models to reduce research specific bias including standardisation, matching of cases and controls, adjustment in multivariate model, stratification, propensity scoring or other methods were appropriately justified</p>
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using valid and reliable measurements OR it is deemed that the measures used would not appreciably bias results (i.e. the authors justified the validity of the measures from previously published research). There is indirect evidence that appropriate adjustments were made for most primary covariates and confounders</p> <p>OR it is deemed that not considering or only considering a partial list of covariates or confounders in the final analyses would not appreciably bias results</p>
		—	<p>There is indirect evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using measurements of unknown validity OR there is insufficient information provided about the measures used. There is indirect evidence that the distribution of primary covariates and known confounders differed between the groups and was not appropriately adjusted for in the final analyses</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about the distribution of known confounders.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is indirect evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using measurements of unknown validity OR there is insufficient information provided about the measures used. There is indirect evidence that the distribution of primary covariates and known confounders differed between cases and controls and was not investigated further</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about the distribution of known confounders in cases and controls</p>
		—	<p>There is direct evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using non valid measurements. There is direct evidence that the distribution of primary covariates and known confounders differed between the groups, confounding was demonstrated and was not appropriately adjusted for in the final analyses.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is direct evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using non valid measurements. There is direct evidence that the distribution of primary covariates and known confounders differed between cases and controls, confounding was demonstrated, but was not appropriately adjusted for in the final analyses</p>
		NA	Not applicable

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
3	<p>Did researchers adjust or control for other exposures that are anticipated to bias results?</p> <p>Examples: background diet (e.g. vegan/vegetarian status, phytoestrogen content of the diet), baseline isoflavones intake from diet, concomitant medication (e.g. antibiotic use, use of hormone replacement therapy), reproductive hormonal factors (e.g. number of children, breast feeding)</p>	++	There is direct evidence that other exposures anticipated to bias results were not present or were appropriately adjusted for. For occupational studies or studies of contaminated sites, other chemical exposures known to be associated with those settings were appropriately considered
		+	There is indirect evidence that other co-exposures anticipated to bias results were not present or were appropriately adjusted for OR it is deemed that co-exposures present would not appreciably bias results. Note, as discussed above, this includes insufficient information provided on co-exposures in general population studies
		–	There is indirect evidence that there was an unbalanced provision of additional co-exposures across the primary study groups, which were not appropriately adjusted for OR there is insufficient information provided about co-exposures in occupational studies or studies of contaminated sites where high exposures to other chemical exposures would have been reasonably anticipated. <u>For case-control studies:</u> There is indirect evidence that there was an unbalanced provision of additional co-exposures across cases and controls, which were not appropriately adjusted for OR there is insufficient information provided about co-exposures in occupational studies or studies of contaminated sites where high exposures to other chemical exposures would have been reasonably anticipated
		—	There is direct evidence that there was an unbalanced provision of additional co-exposures across the primary study groups, which were not appropriately adjusted for. <u>For case-control studies:</u> There is direct evidence that there was an unbalanced provision of additional co-exposures across cases and controls, which were not appropriately adjusted for
		NA	Not applicable
Bias domain: attrition/exclusion bias			
4	<p>Were outcome data incomplete due to attrition or exclusion from analysis?</p> <p>Attrition rates are required to be similar and uniformly low across groups with respect to withdrawal or exclusion from analysis.</p> <p>When withdrawals or incomplete outcome are not similar and uniformly low across groups a bias can be introduced in the estimates</p>	++	<p>There is direct evidence that loss of subjects (i.e. incomplete outcome data) was adequately addressed and reasons were documented when human subjects were removed from a study. Acceptable handling of subject attrition includes very little missing outcome data; reasons for missing subjects unlikely to be related to outcome (for survival data, censoring unlikely to be introducing bias); missing outcome data balanced in numbers across study groups, with similar reasons for missing data across groups</p> <p>OR missing data have been imputed using appropriate methods, AND characteristics of subjects lost to follow up or with unavailable records are described in identical way and are not significantly different from those of the study participants.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is direct evidence that exclusion of subjects from analyses was adequately addressed, and reasons were documented when subjects were removed from the study or excluded from analyses.</p>

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that loss of subjects (i.e. incomplete outcome data) was adequately addressed and reasons were documented when human subjects were removed from a study</p> <p>OR it is deemed that the proportion lost to follow-up would not appreciably bias results. This would include reports of no statistical differences in characteristics of subjects lost to follow up or with unavailable records from those of the study participants. Generally, the higher the ratio of participants with missing data to participants with events, the greater potential there is for bias. For studies with a long duration of follow-up, some withdrawals for such reasons are inevitable.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is indirect evidence that exclusion of subjects from analyses was adequately addressed, and reasons were documented when subjects were removed from the study or excluded from analyses</p>
		-	<p>There is indirect evidence that loss of subjects (i.e. incomplete outcome data) was unacceptably large and not adequately addressed OR there is insufficient information provided about numbers of subjects lost to follow-up.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is indirect evidence that exclusion of subjects from analyses was not adequately addressed</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about why subjects were removed from the study or excluded from analyses</p>
		---	<p>There is direct evidence that loss of subjects (i.e. incomplete outcome data) was unacceptably large and not adequately addressed. Unacceptable handling of subject attrition includes reason for missing outcome data likely to be related to true outcome, with either imbalance in numbers or reasons for missing data across study groups; or potentially inappropriate application of imputation.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is direct evidence that exclusion of subjects from analyses was not adequately addressed. Unacceptable handling of subject exclusion from analyses includes reason for exclusion likely to be related to true outcome, with either imbalance in numbers or reasons for exclusion across study groups</p>
		NA	Not applicable
Bias domain: information/detection bias			
5	<p>Were the outcome assessors blinded to study group or exposure level?</p> <p>Blinding requires that outcome assessors do not know the study group or exposure level of the human subject or animal when the outcome was assessed</p>	++	<p>There is direct evidence that the outcome assessors (including study subjects, if outcomes were self-reported) were adequately blinded to the exposure level, and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding prior to reporting outcomes.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is direct evidence that the outcome assessors (including study subjects, if outcomes were self-reported) were adequately blinded to the exposure level when reporting outcomes</p>
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that the outcome assessors were adequately blinded to the exposure level, and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding prior to reporting outcomes</p> <p>OR it is deemed that lack of adequate blinding of outcome assessors would not appreciably bias results (including that subjects self-reporting outcomes were likely not aware of reported links between the exposure and outcome lack of blinding is unlikely to bias a particular outcome).</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is indirect evidence that the outcome assessors were adequately blinded to the exposure level when reporting outcomes</p> <p>OR it is deemed that lack of adequate blinding of outcome assessors would not appreciably bias results (including that subjects self-reporting outcomes were likely not aware of reported links between the exposure and outcome or lack of blinding is unlikely to bias a particular outcome)</p>

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
		–	<p>There is indirect evidence that it was possible for outcome assessors to infer the exposure level prior to reporting outcomes (including that subjects self-reporting outcomes were likely aware of reported links between the exposure and outcome)</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about blinding of outcome assessors.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is indirect evidence that it was possible for outcome assessors to infer the exposure level prior to reporting outcomes (including that subjects self-reporting outcomes were likely aware of reported links between the exposure and outcome)</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about blinding of outcome assessors</p>
		—	<p>There is direct evidence that outcome assessors were aware of the exposure level prior to reporting outcomes (including that subjects self-reporting outcomes were aware of reported links between the exposure and outcome).</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is direct evidence that outcome assessors were aware of the exposure level prior to reporting outcomes (including that subjects self-reporting outcomes were aware of reported links between the exposure and outcome)</p>
		NA	Not applicable
9	<p>Key question B: Can we be confident in the outcome assessment?</p> <p>Confidence requires valid, reliable and sensitive methods to assess the outcome and the methods should be applied consistently across groups</p>	++	<p>There is direct evidence that the outcome was assessed in cases using well-established methods (the gold standard) and subjects had been followed for the same length of time in all study groups.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is direct evidence that the outcome was assessed using well-established methods (the gold standard)</p>
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that the outcome was assessed in cases (i.e. case definition) using acceptable methods and subjects had been followed for the same length of time in all study groups</p> <p>OR it is deemed that the outcome assessment methods used would not appreciably bias results.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is indirect evidence that the outcome was assessed using acceptable methods</p> <p>OR it is deemed that the outcome assessment methods used would not appreciably bias results</p>
		–	<p>There is indirect evidence that the outcome was assessed in cases using an insensitive instrument or was not adequately validated</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about how cases were identified.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is indirect evidence that the outcome assessment method is an insensitive instrument or was not adequately validated</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about validation of outcome assessment method</p>
		—	<p>There is direct evidence that the outcome was assessed in cases using an insensitive instrument.</p> <p><u>For case-control studies:</u> There is direct evidence that the outcome assessment method is an insensitive instrument</p>
		NA	Not applicable
Bias domain: selective reporting			
7	<p>Were all measured outcomes reported?</p> <p>Selective reporting bias refers to selective inclusion of outcomes in the publication of the study</p>	++	<p>There is direct evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (primary and secondary) outlined in the material and methods, abstract and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported. This would include outcomes reported with sufficient detail to be included in meta-analysis or fully tabulated during data extraction</p>

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
	on the basis of the results. Selective reporting is present if pre-specified outcomes are not reported or incompletely reported. It is likely widespread and difficult to assess with confidence for most studies unless the study protocol is available. Selective reporting bias can be assessed by comparing the 'methods' and 'results' section of the paper, and by considering outcomes measured in the context of knowledge in the field. Abstracts of presentations relating to the study may contain information about outcomes not subsequently mentioned in publications. Selective reporting bias should be suspected if the study does not report outcomes in the results section that would have been expected based on the methods, or if a composite score is present without the individual component outcomes. It may be useful to pay attention to author affiliations and funding source which can contribute to selective outcome reporting when results are not consistent with expectations or value to the research objectives	+	There is indirect evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (primary and secondary) outlined in the material and methods, abstract and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported OR analyses that had not been planned at the outset of the study (i.e. retrospective unplanned subgroup analyses) are clearly indicated as such and it is deemed that the omitted analyses were not appropriate and selective reporting would not appreciably bias results. This would include outcomes reported with insufficient detail such as only reporting that results were statistically significant (or not)
		-	There is indirect evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (primary and secondary) outlined in the material and methods, abstract and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported OR there is insufficient information provided about selective outcome reporting
		---	There is direct evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (primary and secondary) outlined in the material and methods, abstract and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have not been reported. In addition to not reporting outcomes, this would include reporting outcomes based on composite score without individual outcome components or outcomes reported using measurements, analysis methods or subsets of the data (e.g. subscales) that were not pre-specified or reporting outcomes not pre-specified (unless clear justification for their reporting is provided, such as an unexpected effect)
		NA	Not applicable

A3. Appraisal tool for animal studies (adapted from NTP OHAT, online)

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
Bias domain: confounding bias			
1	Key question A: Did the study design or data analysis account for important confounding and modifying variables? <i>Note: a parallel question under detection bias addresses reliability of the measurement of confounding variables.</i> In the context of an animal study, this element would include consideration of covariates such as body weight, or other outcome specific covariates	++	There is direct evidence that appropriate adjustments were made for the relevant covariates. <i>The SYRCLE appraisal tool for animal studies suggests the following baseline characteristics and/or confounders to be described:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the age and/or weight of the animals; baseline values of the outcomes which are of interest in the study
		+	There is indirect evidence that appropriate adjustments were made for the relevant covariates OR it is deemed that not considering or only considering a partial list of covariates or confounders in the final analyses would not appreciably bias results
		-	There is indirect evidence that appropriate adjustments were made for OR there is insufficient information provided about the distribution of known confounders in cases and controls
		---	There is direct evidence that appropriate adjustments were not made for body weight, litter size in studies of offspring (especially when the outcome measure is growth-related and assessed prior to weaning), or any other relevant covariates
		NA	Not applicable

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
2	<p>Did researchers adjust or control for other exposures that are anticipated to bias results?</p> <p>Experimental animal studies need to consider the impact of inadvertent chemical or biological co-exposures. For example, if exposure to chemicals with oestrogenic properties, husbandry practices that raise the background level of oestrogenicity (such as the use of a diet high in phytoestrogens) may make the model system less sensitive to detect low-dose effects. In this case, the direction of the bias would be towards the null (towards smaller effect sizes)</p>	++	There is direct evidence that other exposures anticipated to bias results were not present or were appropriately adjusted for. For oestrogenic exposures or endpoints anticipated to be affected by oestrogenic or endocrine pathways, this would include if animals were fed a phytoestrogen-free or low phytoestrogen diet
		+	There is indirect evidence that other exposures anticipated to bias results were not present or were appropriately adjusted for OR it is deemed that co-exposures present would not appreciably bias results
		–	There is indirect evidence that the control group may have received the treatment or there was an unbalanced provision of additional co-exposures which were not appropriately adjusted for. For oestrogenic exposures or endpoints anticipated to be affected by oestrogenic or endocrine pathways, this would include if animals were likely fed a diet that did not minimise or eliminate phytoestrogen content (or phytoestrogen content of diet was not reported)
		—	There is direct evidence that the control group received the treatment or there was an unbalanced provision of additional co-exposures which were not appropriately adjusted for. For oestrogenic exposures or endpoints anticipated to be affected by oestrogenic or endocrine pathways, this would include that animals were fed a diet that did not minimise or eliminate phytoestrogen content
		NA	Not applicable
3	<p>Were experimental conditions identical across study groups?</p> <p>Housing conditions and husbandry practices should be identical across control and experimental groups because these variables may impact the outcome of interest (Duke et al., 2001; Gerdin et al., 2012). Identical conditions include use of the same vehicle in control and experimental animals. This risk of bias element is included in some tools used to assess animal studies (Krauth et al., 2013). It is acknowledged that given reporting practices it is unlikely</p>	++	There is direct evidence that non-treatment-related experimental conditions were identical across study groups (i.e. the study report explicitly provides this level of detail) and the same vehicle was used in control and experimental animals
		+	There is indirect evidence that the same vehicle was used in control and experimental animals OR it is deemed that the vehicle used would not appreciably bias results. As described above, identical non-treatment-related experimental conditions are assumed if authors did not report differences in housing or husbandry
		–	There is indirect evidence that the vehicle differed between control and experimental animals OR authors did not report the vehicle used
		—	There is direct evidence from the study report that non-treatment-related experimental conditions were not comparable between study groups or control animals were untreated, or treated with a different vehicle than experimental animals

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
	that similarity of conditions will be explicitly reported in most studies. Thus, it is assumed, unless stated otherwise, that experimental conditions (other than use of appropriate vehicle for control animals) were identical across groups which will result in most studies considered 'probably low risk of bias'. In the short-term this risk of bias item is unlikely to be informative for the purposes of discriminating between studies of higher quality and studies of lower quality. However, in the long-term, especially if reporting standards improve, collecting this information may generate data that will allow us to empirically assess evidence of bias or to remove this risk of bias question from consideration. Note, that the use of appropriate vehicle for control animals will remain an important risk of bias consideration	NA	Not applicable

Bias domain: attrition/exclusion bias

4	<p>Were outcome data incomplete due to attrition or exclusion from analysis?</p> <p>Attrition rates are required to be similar and uniformly low across groups with respect to withdrawal or exclusion from analysis</p>	++	<p>There is direct evidence that loss of subjects (i.e., incomplete outcome data) was adequately addressed and reasons were documented when human subjects were removed from a study. Acceptable handling of subject attrition includes: very little missing outcome data; reasons for missing subjects unlikely to be related to outcome (for survival data, censoring unlikely to be introducing bias); missing outcome data balanced in numbers across study groups, with similar reasons for missing data across groups</p> <p>OR missing data have been imputed using appropriate methods, AND characteristics of subjects lost to follow up or with unavailable records are described in identical way and are not significantly different from those of the study participants</p>
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that loss of subjects (i.e. incomplete outcome data) was adequately addressed and reasons were documented when human subjects were removed from a study</p> <p>OR it is deemed that the proportion lost to follow-up would not appreciably bias results. This would include reports of no statistical differences in characteristics of subjects lost to follow up or with unavailable records from those of the study participants. Generally, the higher the ratio of participants with missing data to participants with events, the greater potential there is for bias. For studies with a long duration of follow-up, some withdrawals for such reasons are inevitable</p>
		-	<p>There is indirect evidence that loss of subjects (i.e. incomplete outcome data) was unacceptably large and not adequately addressed</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about numbers of subjects lost to follow-up</p>
		---	<p>There is direct evidence that loss of subjects (i.e. incomplete outcome data) was unacceptably large and not adequately addressed. Unacceptable handling of subject attrition includes: reason for missing outcome data likely to be related to true outcome, with either imbalance in numbers or reasons for missing data across study groups; or potentially inappropriate application of imputation</p>
		NA	Not applicable

Bias domain: information/detection bias

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
5	<p>Were the outcome assessors blinded to study group or exposure level?</p> <p>Blinding requires that outcome assessors do not know the study group or exposure level of the human subject or animal when the outcome was assessed</p>	++	There is direct evidence that the outcome assessors were adequately blinded to the study group, and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding prior to reporting outcomes
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that the outcome assessors were adequately blinded to the study group, and it is unlikely that they could have broken the blinding prior to reporting outcomes</p> <p>OR it is deemed that lack of adequate blinding of outcome assessors would not appreciably bias results, which may vary by outcome (i.e. blinding is especially important for subjective measures).</p> <p>For some outcomes, particularly pathology assessment, outcome assessors are not blind to study group as they require comparison to the control to appropriately judge the outcome, but additional measures such as multiple levels of independent review by trained pathologists can minimise this potential bias</p>
		-	<p>There is indirect evidence that it was possible for outcome assessors (including study subjects if outcomes were self-reported) to infer the study group prior to reporting outcomes</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about blinding of outcome assessors</p>
		—	There is direct evidence for lack of adequate blinding of outcome assessors (including study subjects if outcomes were self-reported), including no blinding or incomplete blinding
		NA	Not applicable
6	<p>Were confounding variables assessed consistently across groups using valid and reliable measures?</p> <p><i>Note: a parallel question under confounding bias addresses whether design or analysis account for confounding.</i></p> <p>Consistent application of valid, reliable, and sensitive methods of assessing important confounding or modifying variables is required across study groups.</p> <p>The requirement for assessing the confounding variables with valid and reliable measures is directly linked to the relative importance of the confounding variable considered under selection bias (i.e., independent of study design, if a confounder needed to be accounted for in design or analyses, then measurement of that variable had to be reliable).</p>	++	There is direct evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using valid and reliable measurements
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence primary covariates and confounders were assessed using valid and reliable measurements</p> <p>OR it is deemed that the measures used would not appreciably bias results (i.e. the authors justified the validity of the measures from previously published research)</p>
		-	<p>There is indirect evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using measurements of unknown validity</p> <p>OR there is insufficient information provided about the measures used</p>
		—	There is direct evidence that primary covariates and confounders were assessed using non valid measurements
		NA	Not applicable
7	<p>Key question B: Can we be confident in the outcome assessment?</p> <p>Confidence requires valid, reliable, and sensitive methods to assess the outcome and the methods should be applied consistently across groups</p>	++	There is direct evidence that the outcome was assessed using well-established methods (the gold standard) assessed at the same length of time after initial exposure in all study groups
		+	<p>There is indirect evidence that the outcome was assessed using acceptable methods (i.e. deemed valid and reliable but not the gold standard) assessed at the same length of time after initial exposure in all study groups</p> <p>OR it is deemed that the outcome assessment methods used would not appreciably bias results</p>

No	Question	Rating	Explanation for expert judgement
		–	There is indirect evidence that the outcome assessment method is an insensitive instrument, the authors did not validate the methods used, or the length of time after initial exposure differed by study group OR there is insufficient information provided about validation of outcome assessment method
		—	There is direct evidence that the outcome assessment method is an insensitive instrument, or the length of follow up differed by study group
		NA	Not applicable
Bias domain: selective reporting			
8	Were all measured outcomes reported? Selective reporting bias refers to selective inclusion of outcomes in the publication of the study on the basis of the results. Selective reporting is present if pre-specified outcomes are not reported or incompletely reported. It is likely widespread and difficult to assess with confidence for most studies unless the study protocol is available. Selective reporting bias can be assessed by comparing the 'methods' and 'results' section of the paper, and by considering outcomes measured in the context of knowledge in the field. Abstracts of presentations relating to the study may contain information about outcomes not subsequently mentioned in publications. Selective reporting bias should be suspected if the study does not report outcomes in the results section that would have been expected based on the methods, or if a composite score is present without the individual component outcomes. It may be useful to pay attention to author affiliations and funding source which can contribute to selective outcome reporting when results are not consistent with expectations or value to the research objectives	++	There is direct evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (primary and secondary) outlined in the material and methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported. This would include outcomes reported with sufficient detail to be included in meta-analysis or fully tabulated during data extraction
		+	There is indirect evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (primary and secondary) outlined in the material and methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported OR analyses that had not been planned at the outset of the study (i.e. retrospective unplanned subgroup analyses) are clearly indicated as such and it is deemed that the omitted analyses were not appropriate and selective reporting would not appreciably bias results. This would include outcomes reported with insufficient detail such as only reporting that results were statistically significant (or not)
		–	There is indirect evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (primary and secondary) outlined in the material and methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have been reported OR there is insufficient information provided about selective outcome reporting
		—	There is direct evidence that all of the study's measured outcomes (primary and secondary) outlined in the material and methods, abstract, and/or introduction (that are relevant for the evaluation) have not been reported. In addition to not reporting outcomes, this would include reporting outcomes based on composite score without individual outcome components or outcomes reported using measurements, analysis methods or subsets of the data (e.g., subscales) that were not pre-specified or reporting outcomes not pre-specified (unless clear justification for their reporting is provided, such as an unexpected effect)
		NA	Not applicable
Precision			
9	Key question C: Are the repeated measurements (if any) on the experimental units treated appropriately? The repeated measurements on the same experimental unit cannot be treated as independent observations since they are correlated. As for the incorrect identification of experimental unit, the effect of an inappropriate treatment of the replicated observations is an overestimation of the precision	++	Definitely appropriate
		+	Probably appropriate
		–	Probably not appropriate
		—	Definitely not appropriate
		NA	Not applicable